

Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena
Philosophische Fakultät
Institut für Anglistik/Amerikanistik

The Self and the Other in Virginia Woolf's Narrative Fiction

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1. Introduction

*Somewhere, everywhere, now hidden, now
apparent in whatever is written down, is the form of a human being.
If we seek to know him, are we idly occupied?*

- Virginia Woolf, from *The Captain's Death Bed and Other Essays* -

No age has been preoccupied with questions of identity and selfhood more than ours. Ever since the dawn of modern societies, fixed social roles and stereotypes have been crumbling away, leaving the individual with an overwhelming range of possibilities. In the contemporary Western world, everybody can be whatever he or she chooses. We are faced with an endless array of choices which is liberating, on the one hand, but can present an immense burden, on the other hand. Filling a social role, such as the role of a mother, a father, a member of the workforce, does not sufficiently define an individual any longer. The big buzz words of today are individuality, self-management, self-advertising, self-refinement and customization. Even the most trivial of choices, such as the type of caffeinated beverages we order at coffee franchises, is made out to be a manifestation of our inherent personality traits. Phenomena such as midlife and identity crises, the pervasiveness of self-help literature and the sheer number of people who call upon the services of psychotherapists or, much less reputable, of astrologers and other such charlatans emphasize the modern-day struggle with concepts such as the self, personality or identity.

It is often said that art anticipates life. For that assertion Shakespeare's *King Lear* is an excellent case in point. The character of Lear finds himself failing in a changing world and "he no longer knows who and what he is, only that his former self is crumbling and

that his identity depends on others”¹. For many critics, *King Lear* presents a foreshadowing of one of the most important modernist topics which, in turn, anticipated present-day issues with selfhood and identity. This was most strikingly done through Virginia Woolf’s innovative and thoughtful approach to the concept of the self, both in her autobiographical writings as well as in her fictional works. Together with a handful of other writers of her time, such as Marcel Proust, James Joyce, or T. S. Elliot she delved into the realms of the psyche and explored the minds and inner workings of her characters, questioning more traditional literary notions of the self and replacing it by the “divided self”, the “split subject”². Her innovation was not only one of topic, however, but also one of technique. Together with James Joyce, she was one of the first authors to utilize the stream-of-consciousness and flight-of-the-mind techniques to express the essence of a human being in entirely novel ways. Many of her works like the novel *The Waves* are so uncompromising and radical in their approach to character layout and depiction, plot and narrative structure that one could easily categorize them as postmodernist literature. By spearheading the avant-garde movement that modernist literature was at her time, she paved the way for a new narrative in the postmodern age.

My first exposure to modernist writing in general, and Virginia Woolf in particular, took place during the first year of my studies when I attended a seminar on modernist short story writers. Next to Woolf’s work, a number of works by James Joyce and Katherine Mansfield were discussed. Even though I was no less impressed by the works of Joyce and Mansfield, two short stories by Virginia Woolf, namely *The Mark on the Wall* and *Kew Gardens*, had the greatest impact on me. The subject matter, structuring of the plot and narrative technique was so unlike anything I had ever encountered before that it sparked in me a lasting fascination and interest. During the course of my studies, I attended another seminar on Virginia Woolf’s autobiographical novels, wrote two term papers on several aspects of her writing and became thoroughly acquainted with the entirety of her work. Her short stories, however, always held the greatest fascination for me. This is not the case with most critics or even most of her readers. Even the writer and Bloomsbury Group member Edward Morgan Forster, one of Virginia Woolf’s most ardent admirers, did not assign any literary importance to them. He

¹ Terry G. Sherwood, *The Self in Early Modern Literature*, Pittsburgh: Duquesne University Press, 2007, p. 1.

² Shlomith Rimmon-Kenan, *A glance beyond doubt: narration, representation, subjectivity*, Columbus, Ohio: Ohio State University Press, 1996, p.12.

expressed his opinion on the short stories that were collected in the compendium called *Monday or Tuesday* on the occasion of delivering a lecture at Cambridge University shortly after her death, thusly: “*Lovely little things, but they seemed to lead nowhere, they were all tiny dots and coloured blobs, they were an inspired breathlessness, they were a beautiful droning or gasping which trusted to luck.*”³

Even taking into consideration Forster’s own literary penchant⁴, this is a curiously dismissive assessment of Woolf’s short fiction. Unfortunately, it has been prevalent in literary criticism even until today. While many of her novels such as *The Waves* were rightly celebrated as masterpieces, her short fiction was almost completely ignored until the publication of Dean Baldwin’s *Virginia Woolf: a study of the short fiction* in 1989. It seems awkward that a member of the Bloomsbury Group like E. M. Forster, who was privy to modernist literary developments, would judge Woolf’s short fiction in such a way. One would expect a complaint such as ‘they seemed to lead nowhere’ from a realist writer, rather than from a Bloomsbury affiliate, even if one takes into consideration that Forster’s own narrative works can only in a limited way be called modernist. This criticism is most likely aimed at the lack of a conclusion, a message or a final normative statement in most of Woolf’s short stories. The reader is not provided with any explanation or interpretation of the (non-)events that are depicted in her stories. There is no teleology in her work and thus, attempting to extract ‘meaning’ from it seems futile and does not do Woolf’s original intention justice. What she meant to do, she said best in her much-quoted essay *Modern Fiction* from 1919: “*Let us record the atoms as they fall upon the mind in the order in which they fall, let us trace the pattern, however disconnected and incoherent in appearance, which each sight or incident scores upon consciousness.*”⁵ It is apparent from this quotation that even this early in her career as a writer she had defined paradigms for her work, as well as that of any writer that was to be categorized as ‘modernist’. Consequently, it can be inferred that the seeming incoherence and fragmentation of her writing was not due to inexperience or immaturity as an author. On the contrary, she purposefully chose her way of writing as a part of her method and in order to achieve an accurate depiction of mental processes and realities. As Nena Skrbic says in *Wild Outbursts of Freedom*, Woolf’s

³ Cf. S. P. Rosenbaum, *The Bloomsbury Group. A Collection of Memoirs and Commentary*, University of Toronto, 1995, p. 226.

⁴ With regards to his literary style and narrative technique he was clearly more of a realist author.

⁵ Virginia Woolf, *Modern Fiction*, in: Lodge, D. [ed.], *20th Century Literary Criticism. A Reader*, London/New York: Longman, 1972.

short stories can be classed as “*momentary post-impressionist portraits, beyond language and translation*”⁶. They are not meant to lead to a singular, objective truth, but rather to provide a glance at the complexity of life. In her uncompromising determination to expand as far as possible into the innermost core of a human being and into the general concept and meaning of ‘being’, she forfeited greater fame and popularity as a writer and sacrificed many other facets of her artistic capability. Only by doing so was she able to contribute to the advancement of literature and to provide her readers with deep insights into the nature of the psyche, consciousness and the self. For these achievements she is to be highly commended. My admiration for her innovative and vanguard approach to reality as expressed in her works is one major reason why I chose to dedicate my thesis to Virginia Woolf’s writing.

Another incentive to choose this topic is its relative obscurity. Virginia Woolf’s novels and essays are well-known and have been thoroughly analyzed and critically acclaimed. Her short fiction, however, has been largely ignored, save for some sporadic essays or references in anthologies and the previously mentioned *Virginia Woolf: A Study of the Short Fiction* by Dean Baldwin. Even after the publishing of Baldwin’s comprehensive analysis, criticism on Woolf’s short fiction remained sparse. Despite her short stories forming a large part of her artistic output, they have not been systematically treated yet and are “*routinely sidelined in favour of her novels*”⁷, to an extent that a number of her short stories have remained unpublished even until the present day. An unploughed field of literary criticism such as this usually provides a more interesting vantage point for a master thesis than a main stream topic. In choosing such a topic, several problems such as the scarcity of secondary literature present themselves, however, at the same time one it offers up a chance for unique and original thought that remains largely free of any preconceived notions one might otherwise have gathered by the intake of other literary viewpoints and opinions.

Undoubtedly, Woolf’s technique is fully developed and brought to the greatest mastery in novels like *To the Lighthouse*, *Mrs. Dalloway*, and *The Waves*. However, her short stories provide all these achievements in a compact and condensed form which serves to

⁶ Nena Skrbic, *Wild outbursts of freedom: reading Virginia Woolf’s short fiction*, Westport: Praeger, 2004, p. xii.

⁷ Skrbic, 2004, p. xiii.

emphasize her concept of reality and the perception thereof as transient, subjective and multi-faceted. In fact, almost all of her short stories deal with topics like consciousness, subjectivity and perspective, identity and the self. Classic examples from her body of short fiction that deal with these topics are *An Unwritten Novel* (1921) or *In the Orchard* (1923). Even more so than in her novels, a characteristic feature of her short stories is her way of writing that one would expect in poetry rather than in prose. The fragmentation and extensive use of metaphor and imagery makes her short fiction prose ambiguous⁸ and requires the active participation of the reader as interpreter. While many of her novels achieve at least some degree of artistic unity and convey to the audience a sense of completion and wholeness, her short fiction leaves us in doubt and struggling with the fact that the only meaning we will be able to prize out of her short fiction is what we lend to it ourselves. In that respect, her work mirrors the human perceptual apparatus. Essentially, the perceptive faculty is always one of creating, of ‘making it up’.⁹ Without knowing it, Woolf anticipated in her works the psychological school of constructivism whose purveyors maintain that human beings are not able to discern an objective truth or reality but rather construct their own realities in their minds. As David Ingersoll states in *Mirror and Metaphor*, human beings are “*strange, wilful creatures who in part accept a given social and natural world, but in part struggle to re-create that world through imagination and action*”.¹⁰ This important contribution to the psychological body of thought comes to the fore most strikingly in her short stories, which is one reason why they are by no means negligible. Naturally, this notion of the subjectivity of perspective does not stop at the perception of the self or the perception of the other. All reality, including images we entertain of others and images we entertain of ourselves, is perspectival, multi-faceted and ambiguous. Nowhere is that emphasized more than in the five short stories I decided to analyze for this thesis. The concept of the self and its perception, however, is not only re-enforced by the plot structure and style of narration Virginia Woolf employed, but is also, quite literally, reflected in the imagery and symbolism. During the course of my studies and through my repeated encounters with Woolf’s writing, I realized early on that one type of symbolism is pervasive throughout her work and especially in her short fiction. That is the symbol of

⁸ Hilde Spiel, *Virginia Woolf. Bildnis einer genialen Frau*, in: Virginia Woolf, *Augenblicke. Skizzierte Erinnerung*, Frankfurt a. Main: Fischer, 1998, p. 15.

⁹ Cf. Michael H. Withworth, *Einstein’s wake: relativity, metaphor and modernist literature*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2001, p. 104.

¹⁰ Daniel W. Ingersoll, *Mirror and metaphor. Material and social constructions of reality*, Lanham: University Press of America, 1981, p. 8.

the mirror. Looking glasses in all variations or forms can be found in many of her short stories, novels and even in some of her non-fictional works along with episodes of mirroring and being mirrored. For many years, it has been one of my greatest literary interests to investigate the significance of this type of symbolism in its relation to Woolf's notions of perception, self-hood and identity and thus, the larger part of this paper will be dedicated to the analysis of stories containing mirror imagery which brings me to a brief overview on the structure of this paper.

Since it is the main objective of this thesis to analyse the relation between Virginia Woolf's idea of the self as seen by oneself as well as others and furthermore to attempt to relate her use of the mirror symbol to that concept, a thorough analysis of the terms 'self' and 'reality' is indispensable. Thus, the opening chapter is dedicated to the investigation of reality perception and concepts of the self in pre-modernist, modernist and postmodernist literature. Several hints as to her understanding of the self and the perception thereof can also be found in Woolf's diaries and letters which is why the subsequent chapter will deal with her concept of selfhood and identity as well as her conflicted attitude towards mirrors as they are laid out in her autobiographical writing. The next chapter will consist of a brief overview on the history of the mirror symbol in literature. In that section, a wide range of examples from Ovid's *Metamorphoses* to contemporary uses will be provided in order to trace the changes in meaning the mirror symbol underwent during the course of the ages and, thus, to understand how writers with a modernist background like Virginia Woolf might have interpreted and used such imagery. Also, since much of Woolf's work pertains to questions of the psyche and the human perceptual apparatus, I found it interesting to include a brief excursion into the topic of psychoanalysis and the influence of the psychoanalytical body of thought on Woolf's writing. This chapter is also supposed to show how Woolf bridges the gap between the school of psychoanalysis and that of constructivism, how elements of both are incorporated into her work and are forged into a unique and original approach to consciousness and self-hood.

The main part of this paper will be devoted to the analysis of five of Woolf's "looking-glass stories", as well as selected passages from the novel *The Waves*. Through the literary analysis of these texts, I will attempt to sketch a picture of Woolf's concept of the self as it is manifested in the perceptions, self-images and interpersonal relationships

of her characters. Moreover, I intend to demonstrate that her characteristic use of mirror imagery in the selected texts enforces these underlying concepts and ideas and serves to communicate them to the reader. As well as considering selected passages from *The Waves*, as previously mentioned, the analysis will mainly draw from five of Woolf's short stories, namely *The New Dress*, *The Legacy*, *Lappin and Lapinova*, *The Mark on the Wall* and *The Lady in the Looking-Glass*. The mirror imagery that is pervasive in these works as well as other passages pertaining to the self¹¹ will be thoroughly investigated with respect to their relationship with one another. In the concluding chapter, an evaluation of the findings will be given and an attempt at putting them into context with my hypotheses will be made. At the very least, it is my hope to do justice to the genius of Virginia Woolf and her works. She deserves to be acclaimed as a brilliant author and dauntless pioneer of modernist literature. To say it with the words of Dean Baldwin, she "*left behind a body of short fiction that will stand favourable comparison with stories of the best of her contemporaries*"¹². We are indeed only just beginning to appreciate her achievement.

¹¹ It is not by accident that these passages often overlap.

¹² Dean R. Baldwin, *Virginia Woolf: a study of the short fiction*, Boston: Twayne, 1989, p. 73.

2. Concepts of the self and reality in fiction

In order to be able to successfully analyze Virginia Woolf's work, it is indispensable to take a glance at a number of terms that will serve as analytical dimensions in this paper. Thus, the following chapter is dedicated to an excursion into the literary concepts of 'reality' and 'the self'.

2.1 The classic realist concept

Literature is often concerned with telling a story and exploring a story world and its characters. When analyzing how such a world, such a reality is presented one will inevitably have to deal with different ideas or concepts of what reality and of what the 'self' is. Whether this reality may be fictional or factual, there is always a process of mediation in literature which requires an underlying structure, a frame of narration. Thus, how a story is told often depends on the author's idea of what reality is and consequently, how it should be portrayed in literature. Many literary styles and their way of relating story-time and story-events correspond with a certain philosophical concept of reality. This concept provides a frame for a narrated reality and narrated self. One of these concepts is the philosophical idea of materialism which claims that matter is the only substance in existence in the world and that all perceivable phenomena are the result of material interaction. Thus, a materialistic view would entail the idea of a singular, objective truth as well as a singular, objective, absolute reality that is the same for every human being and even exists independently of any human being's perception. Associated with this train of thought is a school of writing commonly known as classical realism. Realism in the visual arts as well as in literature is mostly concerned with the depiction of subjects as they appear in everyday life, without embellishment or interpretation. This approach could be described as a "*window onto reality*".¹³ Well-known realists include Gustave Flaubert, Guy de Maupassant and Charles Dickens, as

¹³ Parsons, Deborah, *Theorists of the modernist novel: James Joyce, Dorothy Richardson, Virginia Woolf*, London: Routledge 2007, p. 23.

well as Woolf's literary antagonist Arnold Bennett. One characteristic of classical realism is the use of great external detail which Virginia Woolf described in her frequently quoted essay *Modern Fiction* thusly:

*The writer seems constrained, not by his own free will but by some powerful and unscrupulous tyrant who has him in thrall, to provide a plot, to provide comedy, tragedy, love interest, and an air of probability embalming the whole so impeccably that if all his figures were to come to life they would find themselves dressed down to the last button of their coats in the fashion of the hour.*¹⁴

It is well-known that Woolf herself disliked this style of writing and therefore this description of realism is a little on the polemic side. However, it illustrates the realist dogma of depicting reality 'as it is'. In the realist novel characters are usually portrayed like billiard balls which collide and change each other's direction. For that same reason, the realist method doesn't lead to great psychological depth or insight which is one of the major vantage points for modernist criticism of classic realism. Woolf and other such critics argued that the materialists¹⁵ fail to capture reality, because they make it seem as though it consisted only of social and material phenomena whereas modernists such as Marcel Proust, James Joyce and Virginia Woolf herself are more interested in the 'spiritual'¹⁶ quality of life, by which Woolf means the mind or the consciousness, the inner workings of a character. In *Modern Fiction* she therefore sets a new standard for novel-writing. According to Woolf, modern novels should be concerned with the life of the mind in all its conscious, subconscious and unconscious workings.

2.2 The modernist concept

Whereas the classic realist novel is concerned with describing an objectively perceptible reality by a one-to-one translation into text, "*the question of the nature of reality, and how to capture it in fiction, lies at the foundation of the modernist novel*".¹⁷ In this opposition of literary styles, the paradigms of mimesis and creatio also come to the fore.

¹⁴ Woolf, *Modern Fiction*.

¹⁵ This is Woolf's own term for realist writers. She also uses the juxtaposition of Georgians vs. Edwardians, cf. Parsons, 2007, p. 47.

¹⁶

¹⁷ Parsons, 2007, p. 53.

“Keenly aware that life was more varied than normative generic conventions tended to make it seem”¹⁸ modernist novelists required new ways of expressing their modern ideas. And not only had the modernist writers become aware that reality was more varied than it had been presented in conventional literature – but they also began to suspect that it might be qualitatively different from what it had been believed to be. In the wake of Einstein’s and Heisenberg’s great discoveries in the field of physics many peoples’ concept of reality had changed. The view of a linear, corporeal, coherent, objectively perceptible reality that had been predominant in the 19th century was called into question and replaced with a different concept that emphasized the subjectivity, diversity and the fragmentation of reality and the self. This new concept was reflected in many modernist works of literature, most prominently in the modernist novel. Next to the depiction of character, the two most significant distinctions between the modernist and the classic realist novel are the structuring of plot and the shaping of the narrative. In the conventional realist novel, the reader is provided with a plot that closely follows the prescriptions of Aristotelian dramatic theory¹⁹ and relates the events in an ordered, chronological fashion. It has an exposition through which the reader is introduced to the protagonists and the main plot lines of action, which is followed by rising action, a turning point or a climax of some description and invariably concludes with a resolution, oftentimes in the form of a happy ending. Even when the realist novel ends tragically and however complex the plot structure that leads to this dénouement might be, the realist novel is always narrated towards an end goal and often carries a message or makes a point. In that way it reflects the underlying idea of reality as teleological, linear and meaningful. In contrast, the modernist novel often concerns itself with seemingly trivial, everyday events or is even virtually plotless in some cases.²⁰ The plots of modernist novels usually don’t follow the classic structure of exposition-climax-resolution but are often organized thematically rather than chronologically. Modernist writers often made use of foreshadowing or flashbacks, ellipsis and fragmentation which enforces the underlying idea of the incoherent, multi-faceted nature of reality. The modernist novelist also denies the teleological orientation of literature as well as the teleological orientation of reality and consequently, the modernist novel, as well as the

¹⁸ Ibid.

¹⁹ Cf. M. H. Abrams, *A Glossary of Literary Terms*, Fort Worth [u. a.]: Harcourt Brace College Publ., 1999, p. 224 et seq.

²⁰ A prime example of a plotless novel is Virginia Woolf’s *The Waves*, which is considered as her masterpiece by many critics.

modernist short story, often lacks a ‘punch line’. It creates a feeling of being afloat in a universe without inherent meaning or purpose. However, in opposition to most post-modernist writers, the modernists often struggled with the full consequences of this concept and sought to maintain at least a semblance of both artistic and philosophical unity.²¹ In Joyce’s work and especially in his short fiction this was almost always brought about by a moment of epiphany (which Woolf called ‘moments of being’) that provided some sort of deeper insight or a cathartic element.

2.3 Narration in realist vs. modernist literature and its impact on the portrayal of the self

A second important distinction between classical realist and modernist writing are the different forms of narration that are employed. The predominant mode of narration in classical realism is the omniscient, reliable, third-person narrator. The events are generally told exclusively through the eyes of this narrator figure. The thoughts, emotions and inner workings are related in that way as is every other event in the story. Thus, the reader is presented with a lot of external detail and even descriptions of internal states of characters remain mere quotes, since the emotion or thought is narrated from the outside. This reinforces the realist claim to an objective perception of reality and the self which can be looked at and narrated from the outside, like a diorama of figures that is the same to every spectator. In contrast to that approach, modernist novels and short stories are often presented²² from the inside out, namely from the vantage point of a character’s inner world. Interior monologues attempt to reproduce and simulate the consciousness of a character without any interference by a narrator. Thus, a distinct impression of immediacy is evoked by the employment of interior monologue. In contrast to direct speech or free direct discourse, the narrative distance is much less noticeable in this form of narration. This is especially true for the stream of consciousness technique²³ which is a mode of ‘narration’ that “*undertakes to reproduce*

²¹ This is often achieved by the employment of a recurrent theme, such as the snail in Woolf’s short *The Mark on the Wall*.

²² The term ‘narrated’ often doesn’t apply to the way the action is presented in modernist fiction anymore.

²³ This term was used first by William James in his *Principles of Psychology* (1890), but has especially from the 1920s been adopted to refer to a particular narrative method.

[...] *the full spectrum and continuous flow of a character's mental process, in which sense perceptions mingle with conscious and half-conscious thoughts, memories, expectations, feelings, and random associations.*"²⁴ This mode of narration was particularly well-suited to the modernist quest of portraying a 'look within'²⁵, of accurately presenting the flow of a character's thoughts without mediation or explanation. As one of her main stipulations in her essay on *Modern Fiction* Woolf phrased it like this: "*Let us record the atoms as they fall upon the mind in the order in which they fall, let us trace the pattern, however disconnected and incoherent in appearance, which each sight or incident scores upon the consciousness.*"²⁶ This short description of the modernist way of writing also hints at some further important characteristics of modernism like its concept of self and reality.

2.4 The roots of the modernist concept of the self and reality

The literary movement of modernism is rooted in the changes that took place during the industrial revolution. Along with the industrialisation and streamlining of the workplace there came phenomena such as de-personalization and the loss of individual perspective which spawned modernist art and fiction as a counter current. Additionally, the sciences, particularly physics and psychology, advanced at an astonishing pace and, with their mind-boggling discoveries, changed our perception of what the psyche or the self is dramatically. On December 14th, 1900, Max Planck introduced the world to his famous black-body radiation law which laid the foundation for a new branch of physics. With the help of this new branch, namely quantum physics, scientists were able for the first time to explain and understand phenomena like the particle-wave dualism of light. In 1905, Einstein's theory of relativity followed. It postulated that time and space, contrary to what humankind had believed for thousands of years, were not absolute parameters, not constants, but relative entities. Essentially, what this meant was that time and space and, therefore, the perception of reality depended on the perceiving entity. The last blow for a traditional, static model of the universe was dealt by Werner Heisenberg when he

²⁴ Abrams, 1999, p. 298 et seq.

²⁵ Woolf, *Modern Fiction*, p. 87.

²⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 88.

introduced his uncertainty principle in 1927. This principle states that locating the exact position of a particle in a defined region of space makes the exact measurement of its momentum impossible and vice versa. This was to say that time, space and momentum were not only relative physical entities, but that it was impossible to even determine their value beyond a specific degree of certainty. These groundbreaking discoveries shattered all traditional notions of reality and the perception thereof and, in turn, heavily impacted the presentation of reality in the arts. The idea “*that reality is, in itself, chaotic was the basis for philosophical, [...] linguistic and aesthetic theories in this period*”.²⁷ This is especially true for many modernist writers who modelled their representations of reality in response to these scientific discoveries, industrial revolutions and social overthrows. Their realm of experience had become one of dissociation, fragmentation and uncertainty which are, consequently, reflected in many modernist works.²⁸ Above all, there emerged a new concept of reality as a relative, chaotic, subjective and complex entity which served as a point of reference for almost all modernist writings. An excellent example is Proust’s masterpiece *À la recherche du temps perdu*, which is considered one of the most important 20th century works of fiction. In this novel, Proust focuses on the subjectivity of human perception. It is asserted that a human being cannot objectively perceive truth or reality but is at best able to establish a subjective perception. The modernist idea of each person being a world, a cosmos, a reality unto themselves was first formulated in this work. Making these individual worlds accessible to others is one of the main objectives of modern fiction.

2.5 Beyond modernist notions of self and reality

To put these literary innovations and achievements into context and perspective, it is necessary to have a brief look at the various postmodernist literary and dramatic genres. The term postmodernism pertains to certain currents and tendencies in post-World War II literature such as surrealism, Dadaism, magical realism, the theatre of the abstract and many more that were influenced by modernist ideas and concepts. While maintaining

²⁷ Withworth, Michael H., *Einstein’s wake: relativity, metaphor and modernist literature*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2001, p. 83.

²⁸ *Ibid.*

the penchant for modernist experimentation and relying heavily on techniques such as fragmentation, paradox and unreliable narrators, they also deny and dismiss some modernist ideas and use them as a vantage point for the enhancement of their art form and understanding of the world. Thus, the postmodernist author often eschews or mocks the typical modernist quest for meaning. What both modernist and postmodernist literature have in common is turning away from 19th century classical realism and experimenting with subjectivism and new ways of narrating a story. Both tend to 'look within', examine the inner worlds of their characters and different states of consciousness. Next to James Joyce, Virginia Woolf was one of the first artists who explored deeply into the psychological realm, thought of innovative ways and techniques to adequately present this inner world to her readership and thus, served as a model and vantage point for a counter-draft for many post-modernist writers. One of the most important figures of that literary current is Samuel Beckett. He can be classified as both post-modernist and absurd, since his work contains both modernist and post-modernist elements. On the one hand, he was well acquainted with modernism through his friendship with modernist writers such as James Joyce whilst, on the other hand, his work displays a penchant towards postmodernist techniques and contents. He is frequently referred to as one of the fathers of the postmodern movement in fiction, since he carried modernist innovations, such as the subversion of linear plot structure and time sequence and coherent narration, which were introduced into literature by Woolf and her contemporaries, to new heights. Other well-known post-modernist writers who are indebted to the ideas and innovations of their modernist predecessors include Franz Kafka and Eugene Ionesco, as well as Gabriel Garcia Marquez of whom it is known that he was influenced especially by the works of James Joyce and Virginia Woolf.

3. Psychoanalysis and its influence on modernist literature

Next to the discoveries and achievements of Einstein, Planck and other physicists and their impact on modernist literature, which was described in the preceding chapter, one of the most important influences on modernist writing was the advancement of psychology as a science at the end of the 19th century. Many modernist authors were especially impacted in their way of writing by the new theory of psychoanalysis. The term psychoanalysis refers to a psychological theory developed by Sigmund Freud. Along with a new, innovative approach to treating psychopathological phenomena, it provided a generally applicable theory of the self and its motivations. This new theory postulated the division of the human psyche into a subconscious, a conscious and a preconscious realm, which correspond to the three governing entities of the mind: id, ego and superego. Essentially, the theory of psychoanalysis can be described in terms of three basic assumptions; namely, the impact of childhood experiences on personality development, the doctrine of repression and the concept of the unconscious and with it the inability of the self to fully know itself.²⁹

3.1 The significance of psychoanalytical concepts for modernist literature

For the advancement of literature from the classical realist dogma to modernist forms of writing the last two assumptions were especially important. It is not accidental that the rise of psychology as a science and the emergence of the theory of psychoanalysis coincide with the introduction of new literary techniques such as the ‘stream of consciousness’ or the ‘flight of the mind’ technique which aim to represent and explore the inner workings of a character’s mind. Even though the influence that these new psychological theories had on modernist literature is not disputed, there has always been a controversial debate concerning the impact they had on Virginia Woolf’s life and work. Woolf herself had always been quite adamant in her claim that she and other

²⁹ Cf “Psychoanalyse.” *Lexikon der Psychologie*, 1998, p. 848-63.

modernist writers were “*sharply cut off from [their] predecessors*”³⁰ and thus, denied being indebted to any other cultural or scientific currents. However, she also believed that all artists are receptacles of a continuous cultural heritage and tradition. The current state of research regarding Virginia Woolf and psychoanalysis is thoroughly discussed in *Psychoanalyse in der englischen Moderne* by Matthias Munsch. As he points out, research on this topic has always been and remains highly controversial. However, there are certain tendencies to be recognized.

3.2 Discussion of Virginia Woolf’s knowledge of psychoanalysis

Until the 1970s, Virginia Woolf’s possible knowledge of and involvement with psychoanalysis had been largely ignored or only treated marginally and an impact on her literary work had been ruled out. Until that time very little autobiographical material had been available, so that researchers had had no access to Woolf’s own opinion and thoughts on the topic. A first hint that she might have been much better acquainted with psychoanalysis than most literary critics had believed was the discovery that she was the author of the anonymously published review titled *Freudian Fiction*.³¹ After her letters and diaries had been published, the lack of autobiographical sources was eliminated. However, even by means of these personal testimonies it remained difficult to determine what Woolf’s view on Freud and his theories had been, since her own commentary was not consistent throughout her life. What can safely be dismissed as a stark understatement is her claim that she knew of psychoanalysis “*only in the ordinary way of conversation*”³². Woolf, along with her husband Leonard, was a member of the so-called ‘Bloomsbury Group’, a loose association of English artists and intellectuals who had a significant impact on modernist thought and art. Other members were E.M. Forster, Lytton and James Strachey, Clive Bell, Roger Fry and John Maynard Keynes. From as early as 1912, psychoanalysis and Freud had been a topic of interest to several members of the group and was therefore often debated at their meetings in Bloomsbury.

³⁰ Virginia Woolf, *The essays of Virginia Woolf. Vol. 3: 1919-1924*, edited by Andrew McNeillie, London: Hogarth Press, 1995. p. 357.

³¹ Cf. Matthias Munsch, *Psychoanalyse in der englischen Moderne*, Marburg: Verlag Literaturwissenschaft.de, 2004. p. 119

³² *Ibid.*, p. 135.

Since Virginia Woolf is known to have actively participated in intellectual exchange within the group, it is safe to infer that her knowledge of psychoanalytical ideas far exceeded a passing familiarity. This becomes apparent when one keeps in mind that the Strachey brothers were both members of the Society for Physical Research. Moreover, James Strachey and his wife Alix, as well as Virginia Woolf's brother Adrian with his wife Karin had decided to set up in practise as psychoanalysts. Through them Woolf was closely linked with England's preeminent psychoanalysts of that time.³³ Next to the Stracheys and her own brother, her husband Leonard was soon an ardent admirer of Freud and his theories. Consequently, many of Freud's works such as the *Collected Papers* (1924-1950) and the *Standard Edition of the Complete Psychological Works of Sigmund Freud* (1953-66) were published by Hogarth Press of which Virginia Woolf was the co-editor.³⁴ From this brief overview one can already conclude that Woolf had decidedly too many contact points with psychoanalysis to not have been influenced by its main ideas in some way. When approached about the topic directly, however, she denied that psychoanalysis had any influence on her work, or even that she knew much of it: "*I have not studied Dr Freud or any psychoanalyst – indeed I think I have never read any of their books; my knowledge is merely from superficial talk. Therefore, any use of their methods must be instinctive.*"³⁵ This statement dating from 1932 is, as was already assessed, a severe understatement. It is interesting, however, to investigate Woolf's reasons for responding in this particular way. It might very well be the case that she simply did not want to expose herself to possible accusations of unoriginal thought which seems to be indicated by the rest of the quote: *So far as I know, my methods are my own; and not consciously at any rate derived from any other writer.*³⁶

In a predominantly male business like the literary realm of the early 1900s in which women writers still had a very difficult standing, it must have been of the utmost importance not to appear to be in the intellectual debt of a male colleague. That this self-assertion in her role as a female writer was a recurrent topic for her, becomes apparent at the perusal of her extended essay *A Room of One's Own* which was published in 1929 und deals with the question of whether and under what circumstances a female writer is capable of creating literary works of as high a quality as those of male

³³ Cf. *ibid.*, p. 128 et seq.

³⁴ Cf. *ibid.*, p. 61 et seq.

³⁵ Munsch, 2004, p. 135.

³⁶ *Ibid.*

writers. Interestingly enough, she describes the circumstance of the female sex by using the mirror symbol. She maintains that “*women have served all these centuries as looking-glasses possessing the magic and delicious power of reflecting the figure of man at twice its natural size.*”³⁷ What she points to with this analogy is the fact that men need the inferiority of the female sex for their own self-aggrandizement³⁸ “*for if [women] were not inferior, they would cease to enlarge*”³⁹. Naturally, Woolf would decidedly reject any perceived insinuation that she might be considered as such a mirror for a male colleague and thus, by way of precaution disclaim any association or involvement with the respective author’s ideas.

3.3 Virginia Woolf’s ambivalent attitude towards psychoanalysis

Another explanation might be derived from the statements she makes in her diaries. The plethora of her comments on psychoanalysis in these documents reveals Virginia Woolf’s ambivalent attitude towards and opinion on psychoanalysis. On the one hand, the reader is provided with impassioned rejections of the psychoanalytical body of thought and violent attacks on its purveyors, while on the other hand there are a several appreciative comments. According to Munsch’s analysis of the autobiographical sources, Woolf’s occasional hostility towards psychoanalysis can be attributed to unpleasant experiences she made during the times when she was treated for her own mental health issues.⁴⁰ He argues that it is entirely possible that her dismissive, even aggressive demeanour stemmed from her own anxieties. This reasoning is supported by the fact that whenever Woolf was not directly and personally affected by the topic, she was very well capable of critically acclaiming the merits of the new theory and evaluating its significance for the advancement of literature objectively. This became apparent in several of her diary entries as well as in some of her critical writing. On May 18th, 1924, for instance, she gave a lecture before the Cambridge Heretics Society

³⁷ Virginia Woolf, *A Room of One’s Own*, London: Penguin Books, 2004, p 41.

³⁸ Rachel Bowlby, “The Trained Mind: A Room of One’s Own”, in: *Virginia Woolf. A Collection of Critical Essays*, edited by Margaret Homans, Englewood Cliffs (New Jersey): Prentice Hall, 1993, p. 189.

³⁹ *Ibid.*

⁴⁰ Cf. Munsch 2004, p. 131.

using a draft of her essay *Character in Fiction* in which she acknowledged Freud's influence on modernist thought thusly:

No generation since the world began has known quite so much about character as our generation... The average man or woman today thinks more about character than his or her grandparents; character interests them more; they get closer, they dive deeper into the real emotions and motives of their fellow creatures. [...]. If you read Freud, you know in ten minutes some facts - or at least some possibilities - which our parents could not have guessed for themselves.⁴¹

Here Woolf chooses Freud as the representative of scientists of the mind and her assessment clearly shows that she did not generally reject his theories, but, on the contrary, valued Freud's contribution to the investigation of the human psyche and to motivational research. It is also known that she came to esteem him enough to sign an honorific address on the occasion of Sigmund Freud's 80th birthday and visited him and his family in Hampstead in 1939. With respect to her own study of Freud, it can be said that she probably did not attempt to read any of his works herself before 1939. This can be inferred by her diary entry on December 2nd, 1939, where she acknowledges that she "*began reading Freud last night*"⁴². An immediate link between her own perusal and the majority of her works can therefore not be postulated. However, a reverberation of psychoanalytical concepts and themes is clearly noticeable in her writing. For instance, in several of her fictional as well as non-fictional works from as early as 1920 she frequently uses terminology that is associated with Freud and psychoanalysis, such as conscious, subconscious, inferior complex and others.⁴³ One does surely not go wrong in the assumption that despite not having read Freud herself until very late in her life, Virginia Woolf's sensitive antennae had picked up on scientific and artistic currents of that time and that she then incorporated them into her writing. Especially the concept of dividing the mind into a conscious and a subconscious realm appears to have left an impression on her as it is a recurrent theme in such a great number of her short stories and novels. Interestingly, one of Freud's quotes on the topic of the unconscious describes Woolf's method of writing rather vividly and accurately:

⁴¹ Virginia Woolf, *Character in Fiction*, in: McNeillie, Andrew [ed.], *The Essays of Virginia Woolf*, Vol.III, 1919-1924, London: Hogarth Press, 1995.

⁴² Virginia Woolf, *The Diary of Virginia Woolf*, edited by Anne Olivier Bell, assisted by Andrew McNeillie, Volume V, San Diego [et. al.]: Harcourt Brace Jovanovich, 1984, p. 248.

⁴³ Munsch 2004, p. 139.

*“The conscious mind may be compared to a fountain playing in the sun and falling back into the great subterranean pool of subconscious from which it rises.”*⁴⁴

This same idea can be found in several of Virginia Woolf’s works only slightly differently worded. In *To the Lighthouse*, for instance, she speaks of the mind as “*a pool of thought, a deep basin of reality*”⁴⁵. Another example is a quote from *The Mark on the Wall* where the protagonist asserts that she wants to “*sink deeper and deeper, away from the surface, with its hard separate facts*”⁴⁶. At the same time, this statement is a meta-fictional comment on the narrational structure of the entire short story in which the protagonist weaves in and out of different states of mind – plunging into the depths of the preconscious only to resurface again into the conscious world of “*hard, separate facts*”⁴⁷. By means of these examples, it is quite clear that even though Woolf might not have actively studied Freud until 1939, the scientific currents of that time and the circulation of psychoanalytical ideas and concepts in her group of friends heavily influenced her work in semantics, structure and content, especially abetting her modernist preoccupation with issues such as consciousness, perception, reality, the self and its identity. As was outlined in the introductory chapter, Woolf’s fascination with this range of topics and her perspective on them became manifest in her use of the mirror as a literary symbol which will be dealt with in more detail in the following chapter.

⁴⁴ Peter MacDonald [ed.], *Oxford Dictionary of Medical Quotations*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2004, p. 37.

⁴⁵ Virginia Woolf, *To the Lighthouse*, London [et. al.]: Penguin Books, 1996, p. 152.

⁴⁶ Virginia Woolf, *The Mark on the Wall and Other Short Fiction* (Oxford World’s Classics), Oxford [et. al.]: Oxford University Press, 2001, p. 5.

⁴⁷ *Ibid.*

4. The mirror as a literary symbol

Since this paper employs the literary symbol of the mirror as an analytical dimension and attempts to link it to Woolf's understanding of the self, it is necessary to clarify what the term 'symbol' refers to in general and in what ways the mirror has been used in literature from antiquity until modernism. Moreover, there will be a brief examination of the mirror as a literary symbol during the literary epoch of modernism. Special attention is devoted to the augmentation of the range of possible meanings this particular symbol acquired with the rise of modernist literature.

4.1 Symbols in literature

The English word 'symbol' derives from the Greek word *symbolon* which is composed of the prefix *syn-*, meaning 'together' and the root word *bolē* which means 'throw'.⁴⁸ Combined, these two result in an approximate meaning of 'to throw together', which is exactly what a literary symbol is supposed to achieve. It establishes a connection between two otherwise unrelated concepts. A symbol is usually a concrete object or person that stands for an abstract idea, concept or emotion. What is coincidental about symbols is that they are arbitrarily chosen, which is to say that there rarely is an inherent or logical relationship with the entity or phenomenon they symbolize. One counterexample would be a skull that is used to symbolize death. On the other hand, an example of an arbitrary symbol would be a red octagonal sign that is taken to mean 'stop' in most Western countries. Aside from the distinction between arbitrary and non-arbitrary symbols one can categorize symbols as either conventional or non-conventional.⁴⁹ Universal or conventional symbols are understood by most human beings. They "*embody universally recognized meanings whenever used*"⁵⁰ such as the Christian cross. The unconventional or constructed symbol, on the other hand, does not

⁴⁸ Duden – Deutsches Universalwörterbuch, 6., überarbeitete Auflage, Mannheim [et. al.]: Dudenverlag, 2007.

⁴⁹ Cf. Uwe Spörl, *Basislexikon der Literaturwissenschaft*, Paderborn [et. al.]: Schöningh, 2004, p. 112.

⁵⁰ Robert Harris, *Evaluating Internet Research Sources*. VirtualSalt. 17 Nov. 1997. 26 Oct 2008. <<http://www.virtualsalt.com/evalu8it.htm>>.

carry such a universal meaning, but can only be understood in context. Most literary symbols are arbitrary, non-conventional signs in that they point at meanings that go beyond their literal significance and are assigned their symbolic meaning by the way they are used in a specific text. Therefore, literary symbols are usually contextual. A much-cited example of a literary symbol is the white whale in *Moby Dick*.⁵¹ In Melville's novel it is used to signify evil, even though neither the color white nor the whale as an animal have any intrinsic relationship with the concept of 'evil'. Naturally, it still retains its significance as a literal whale. However, it is also associated with a range of meanings that refer to complex, abstract ideas. This significance that the whale is given in the story does not easily carry over into other literary works. Thus, the white whale is a purely contextual symbol. Symbols and metaphors, amongst other literary devices, distinguish literary works from mere reproductions of life and reality. By providing a text with several layers of meaning they create ambiguity and a need for interpretation. Thereby, symbols emphasize the ambiguous and referential nature of literature.⁵²

4.2 The mirror as a literary symbol from antiquity to modernist literature

One of the oldest and most commonly used literary symbols is the mirror. This is to be expected since the mirror is the only device that enables humans to look at their own face and, thus, see himself or herself. No other item could serve as a more suitable symbol of self-knowledge or, reversely, the "inability to know oneself".⁵³ In the form of smooth and polished surfaces or unruffled pools of water, mirrors have been available to mankind from the earliest of times and must have been one of the first things to prompt 'reflections' on the self and on reality. Another reason for its popularity is its unusual literary versatility. A great variety of concepts can be hinted at by using the mirror symbol. It can signify a wide range of abstract ideas including narcissism, egocentricity, reflection, duality, ambiguity, illusion and disillusionment, appearance

⁵¹ Ibid.

⁵² Cf. Dieter Burdorf/Christoph Fasbender/Burkhard Moenninghoff [ed.], *Metzler Lexikon Literatur*, Stuttgart [et. al.]: Metzler, 2007, p. 744 et seq.

⁵³ Jean-Charles Seigneuret [ed.], *Dictionary of literary themes and motifs*, New York [et. al.]: Greenwood Press, 1988, p. 851.

and reality, the self, the psyche and many more. It can function as the intersection of the known and the unknown, the conscious and the subconscious, it can distinguish reality from the semblance of reality and it can reflect the inner conflict of a person.⁵⁴ Moreover, it is often used as a symbol for humankind's inability to fully understand reality which is already hinted at in the thirteenth chapter of Paul's First Epistle to the Corinthians:

*“For now, we see through a glass, darkly; but then face to face: now I know in part; but then shall I know, even as also I am known.”*⁵⁵

Naturally, religious embellishment has little impact on present-day usage of the mirror as a literary symbol; however, the philosophical problem it poses has been significant for writers throughout the times. Epistemological questions of whether human beings can adequately perceive 'reality' or 'truth' were also at the heart of modernist writing and were often hinted at by the use of mirror symbolism. Another early use of mirror symbolism can be found in the Greek myth of Narcissus, one version of which has survived in Ovid's *Metamorphoses*. In that myth, as in most mirror tales of that time, the mirror is used to symbolize self-love and navel-gazing. Narcissus falls in love with a reflection in a pond not knowing that it is his own effigy and, when he eventually attempts to kiss the image, is so disappointed by the truth that he kills himself with his own sword. Indeed, such tales of self-love remained vastly popular well into the 16th century.

With the beginning of the Shakespearean era, however, the mirror symbol acquires a new meaning. Certain virtuous people are referred to as 'mirrors' for other people to look at and model themselves after the reflection. This becomes apparent in phrases such as "mirror of all Christian kings" which characterizes Henry V as an ideal for all Christian kings in Shakespeare's drama of the same name. This is to imply that everyone else should model themselves after this ideal so that when they look at that person it is as though they are looking into a mirror.⁵⁶

⁵⁴ Ralf Konersman, *Spiegel und Bild: zur Metaphorik neuzeitlicher Subjektivität*, Würzburg: Königshausen+Neumann, 1988.

⁵⁵ 1 Cor. 13: 12-13, KJV.

⁵⁶ Michael Ferber, *A Dictionary of Literary Symbols*, Cambridge [et. al.]: Cambridge University Press, 2002, p. 124.

4.3 The mirror as a literary symbol in modernist literature

Whilst romantic and Victorian writers did not contribute many new elements or readings to mirror symbolism, that kind of imagery lends itself easily to modernist notions of the fragmented self. The transition phase from the Victorian age to modernist writing was marked by the emergence of the symbolist and fin de siècle movements. One of the most eminent authors of that time was Oscar Wilde who anticipated the modernist preoccupation with the self in his masterpiece *The Picture of Dorian Gray*. In this novel the protagonist has a portrait of himself painted which ages in his stead. While he remains young and handsome, his decadent, immoral and excessive behavior leaves its mark on his counterpart in the picture. It serves as a reflection of Dorian Gray's character which is made clear when it is said that "*this portrait would be to him the most magical of mirrors. As the portrait had revealed to him his own body, so it would reveal to him his own soul.*"⁵⁷ This was one of the first hints at the modernist use of the mirror symbol. To the modernists, reality and, with it, phenomena such as personality, character and the self ceased to be absolute, consistent and determined entities. Indeed, they ceased to be entities that the human mind was even capable to grasp the full scope of. The traditional notions pertaining to these phenomena such as an "*inalienable essence*"⁵⁸, unity and uniqueness were replaced with rather different concepts of the self. Along with this change in concepts the traditional meanings and reference points of literary symbols were altered considerably. For the modernists, the mirror, for example, is not a means of objectifying and concerning self-knowledge anymore, but becomes a symbol of the desperate, modern-day quest for meaning and identity. Where it once offered security and a "*foothold in the flux of reality*"⁵⁹, it is now a "*sphinx*"⁶⁰ that reflects us back onto ourselves. Consistently, in most modernist novels and stories, and particularly in Virginia Woolf's writing, mirrors often symbolize a fragmented, fragile, elusive self, as well as the struggle for and loss of identity. Her mirrors show different things to different people or even different things to the same person at different times. They reflect only what we bring to them – our anxieties, our insecurities, our inner struggles and our delusions.

⁵⁷ Cf. Oscar Wilde, *The Picture of Dorian Gray*, Ch. 8.

⁵⁸ Rimmon-Kenan, 1996, p. 12.

⁵⁹ Seigneuret, 1988, p. 85.

⁶⁰ Cf. *Ibid.*

Similarly to her works of fiction, most of her autobiographical documents are centered around topics of identity and selfhood, pertaining to herself and others as well as general deliberations on these issues. Especially in her diaries she often reflected on such matters and, by her own admission, considered her letters to be mirrors which “give back a reflection of the other person”.⁶¹ Thus, the mirror is “an arresting image for her epistolary method”⁶² as well as her diary writing, both of which will be the subject of the following chapter.

⁶¹ Virginia Woolf, *The Letters of Virginia Woolf*, edited by Nigel Nicolson, Volume 4, London: Hogarth, 1978, p. 98.

⁶² *Ibid.*, p. xiv.

5. The autobiographical legacy of Virginia Woolf

One of the most widely discussed topics in literary criticism is that of the meaning of a literary work. Whereas some literary scholars argue that the meaning is constructed by every individual reader, a second school maintains that the meaning of a text can only be what the author intended it to be. Today, the most common take on this question is that a successful interpretation of any literary work will have to take into account aspects of inherent, constructed sense as well as the meaning possibly intended by the author in order to arrive at a comprehensive assessment. Unfortunately, it is not always possible to elicit what the author's original intention might have been, since only a few writers care to clarify their meaning or to keep any other personal records that speak on such matters for posterity. Wherever such documents do survive, however, they often help illuminate the author's attitude towards his or her own writing. Luckily, in Virginia Woolf's case many letters and diary entries have been preserved and published by her husband Leonard Woolf. Thus, we are provided with enough autobiographical material to be able to extract Virginia Woolf's perspective and opinion on several topics from it. Oftentimes, in attempting to analyze and interpret a work of fiction, one can only rely on one's literary and scholarly instincts. In dealing with Virginia Woolf's works, however, one finds oneself in the happy circumstance of being able to base research and assessment on a large body of autobiographical testimonies. These are especially useful when attempting to ascertain the writer's perspective on abstract and elusive concepts such as consciousness, the self and reality. From the thorough study of her letters and diaries, it can be maintained that Virginia Woolf's literary works present an accurate reflection of her every-day notions of these concepts as they are manifested in her personal documents. Or, assessed from a different angle, it could be said that she had a penchant for pouring the private thoughts and anxieties that she entertained about these topics⁶³ into her writing. In her diaries and letters, she speaks eloquently on a wide range of ideas pertaining to this thesis, including consciousness and reality, her writing and the design of her characters, the self and the human psyche as well as the self and the other. A good vantage point for a detailed analysis is her take on reality and consciousness and how the two are linked, since Woolf's understanding of reality and

⁶³ As apparent in her autobiographical documents.

how it is perceived by human beings is essential to the style and content of her writing. Interestingly enough, her diaries and letters contain a large number of allusions to and reflections on the nature of the material world and the realms of the human psyche of which none, however, date earlier than 1909 at which time she was already 27 years old. That was also the time around which she began to seriously pursue her career as a writer and started publishing articles and essays on a larger scale. Thus, it is surely not a stretch of the imagination to assume that this co-occurrence was by no means coincidental. Much harder to determine is the causal relation of the two. Was it that her interest in these and other topics increased by such degrees that she felt the urge to write about them or did her writing enforce her inclination for contemplation? In either case, the preoccupation with these issues was a lasting one and was only gradually superseded by different, yet related topics later in her life.

5.1 Virginia Woolf on the world and reality

The first letter, in which she speaks of the real world around her and how it translates to concepts in her mind, was addressed to Clive Bell, her sister's husband, and written on December 26th, 1909. In this letter she describes one of her frequent and usually solitary walks and how the impressions gathered on that walk are moulded into cognitions:

What with the silence, and the possibility of walking out, at any moment, over long wonderfully coloured roads to cliffs with the sea beneath, and coming back past lighted windows to one's tea and fire and book – and then one has thoughts and conceptions of the world and moments like a dragon fly in air...⁶⁴

In this description, the belief in the duality of the material world of things and the mental world of perceptions and ideas⁶⁵ that plays a major role in many of her novels and short stories is already indicated. Another pervasive theme, namely that of the transience of reality, is hinted at by likening moments in time and space to a dragon fly

⁶⁴ Virginia Woolf, *Congenial Spirits. Selected Letters*, edited by Joanne Trautmann Banks and with a new preface by Hermione Lee, London: Pimlico/Random House, 2003, p. 57.

⁶⁵ Woolf's affinity to Plato's philosophy of the 'world of ideas' becomes apparent in many of her autobiographical writings, as well as in her fiction.

hovering in the air. This concept of reality is reflected in her fragmented and ‘breathless’ style of writing. Despite this ever-present notion of elusiveness and evanescence, there is always the desire to find meaning amidst the whirl of impressions, the quest of the human mind for the “*centre of things*”⁶⁶ which she expresses in her diary entry from October 18th, 1918. This impression of a desire to extract meaning from life, of a longing to see the bigger ‘pattern’ is re-enforced in a letter to her friend Gerald Brenan dating from August 1923 in which she writes that she wants to “*arrive at some concept of the meaning of all things*”⁶⁷. In the same paragraph it is made clear by what means she intends to arrive at such a concept:

*Every book is to me a glass through which I may possibly behold – I don’t know what; and so with people; and so with my solitary walks on the downs, when suddenly I find I am breaking through myriads of white convolvulus, twined about the grass...*⁶⁸

This is an allusion to her concept of ‘moments of being’ that is in constant conflict with the modernist theme of fragmentation. Akin to Joyce’s idea of ‘epiphany’, these moments of being are instances of a sudden realization, glimpses at the centre of reality which holds all things together.⁶⁹

5.2 Virginia Woolf on consciousness and the mind

In the following years, however, this thematic constellation is somewhat eclipsed by Woolf’s preoccupation with consciousness or, as she often calls it, the ‘soul’.⁷⁰ Entries about that topic are prevalent well into the year 1926 where a remarkable diary entry

⁶⁶ Virginia Woolf, *A moment’s liberty. The Shorter Diary*, edited by Anne Olivier Bell, Introduction by Quentin Bell, London: Hogarth Press, 1990, p. 59.

⁶⁷ Woolf, *Selected Letters*, p. 176.

⁶⁸ *Ibid.*

⁶⁹ Cf. Vera Nünning, *Die Ästhetik Virginia Woolfs: eine Rekonstruktion ihrer philosophischen und ethischen Grundanschauungen auf der Basis ihrer nicht-fiktionalen Schriften*, Frankfurt a. M.: Lang, 1990, p. 46 et seq.

⁷⁰ It is important to note that Woolf was an atheist and therefore this choice of words is not of a religious nature, but rather a more ‘poetic’ word that pertains to emotions more than the terms ‘mind’ or ‘consciousness’.

signifies the transition from the topic of the human mind back to more universal questions. In this entry dating from February 27th, 1926, she goes from discussing the qualities of the soul to the question of what life is. Here, she resumes her earlier discussion of the nature of reality:

Why is there not a discovery in life? Something one can lay hands on and say 'This is it'? What is it? And shall I die before I can find it? Then (as I was walking through Russell Square last night) I see mountains in the sky: the great clouds, and the moon which is risen over Persia; I have a great and astonishing sense of something there, which is 'it'.⁷¹

This is a topic which must have occupied her mind greatly since it reverberates throughout her work, with the most prominent example being *The Mark on the Wall*, and also keeps recurring in subsequent diary entries such as her deliberations on whether life is “*very solid, or very shifting?*”⁷² Again, she struggles with the antagonistic notions of transitoriness and flux on the one hand and steadiness and solidity on the other hand. This struggle is directly linked to Woolf’s idea that through her writing she might be able to transcend the constant flux of reality and arrive at an eternal truth or at least some sort of pattern of life.⁷³ She spent the remaining years of her life as a writer oscillating back and forth between these two ideas. Feeling herself ‘sinking’ or ‘falling’ away from the surface of reality, unable to hold onto a “*robust sense of fact*”⁷⁴, she was constantly trying to steady herself by any means available. Sometimes her work provided temporary refuge from the uncertainty of reality – “*more than that, I cannot get my sense of unity and coherency and all that makes me wish to write the Lighthouse*”⁷⁵ – and at other times she held fast to others in order not to be torn apart in the vortex of perceptions and emotions: “*I look at you and (being blind to most things except violent impressions) think if Ethel can be so downright and plainspoken and on the spot, I need not fear instant dismemberment by wild horses.*”⁷⁶ All of these statements make it quite clear that for Virginia Woolf reality was by no means static, fixed or unalterable. Quite to the contrary, her personal documents exude a sense of uncertainty, transitoriness and volatility pertaining to that subject matter. The

⁷¹ Woolf, *The shorter diary*, p. 206.

⁷² *Ibid.*, entry from January 4th, 1929, p. 257.

⁷³ *Ibid.*, entry from June 23rd, 1929, p. 262.

⁷⁴ Woolf, *Selected letters*, p. 269.

⁷⁵ *Ibid.*

⁷⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 282.

essence of all these statements is that all we can know of reality are temporary, fragmented impressions which our conscious minds then attempt to process and interpret as accurately as possible.

5.3 Virginia Woolf on the self

One of Woolf's most important basic assumptions on the nature of things which applies to her view of the human mind and the self alike is this ephemeral and amorphous quality. The self and the mind, to her, are multi-faceted entities and essentially subject to constant readjustment and restructuring. According to Woolf, we do not consist of one indivisible self or one consistent personality but are comprised of a myriad of scraps and fragments which gather together in ever-changing patterns and form temporary character constellations. This outlook on the self is laid out in her attempt to explain the character constellation of *The Waves* in a letter to G. L. Dickinson:

But I did mean that in some vague way we are the same person, and not separate people. The six characters were supposed to be one. I'm getting old myself – I shall be fifty next year; and I come to feel more and more how difficult it is to collect oneself into one Virginia; even though the special Virginia in whose body I live for the moment is violently susceptible to all sorts of separate feelings.⁷⁷

For Woolf, the variance was caused mostly by the impact other people had on her. For different people, she was a different Virginia. She views the self as a construct of the people and things it is surrounded with. As susceptible as she was to all kinds of impressions and emotions, the influence that others had on her was tremendous. She struggled her entire life to maintain the centre of her personality but could never do without the relations with others which helped her create herself. In the introduction to *Congenial Spirits*, Joanne Trautmann Banks likens her epistolary method to that of a spider that spins an intricate web of letters with the strands of the different aspects of

⁷⁷ Woolf, Selected Letters, p. 298.

her identity attached to her various friends.⁷⁸ This interdependence of selves, their mutual construction and deconstruction became one of the major motifs in Woolf's works. This is most lucidly reflected in the offer of "*let me then create you*"⁷⁹ that Bernhard extends to Neville in *The Waves*, but also pervades most of her short fiction, particularly stories like *The Legacy* or *Lapin and Lapinova*. Indeed, amongst the range of topics pertaining to the self and identity, the theme of the self in its relation to the other is one of the most prominent. Entire novels like the previously mentioned *The Waves* or also *To the Lighthouse* and *Mrs. Dalloway* revolve around the issue and an even larger number of her short stories can be interpreted as a manifestation of Woolf's preoccupation with the self per se and the self in relation to others. Prime examples are stories like *The New Dress* or *The Lady in the Looking-Glass*. Naturally, seeing how that topic is prevalent in a large part of her work, one would expect it to frequently emerge in her autobiographical documents as well. And indeed, from the onset of her career as a writer until the end of her life this topic stayed with her and even became more prevalent as the years passed. A large part of her own association with others had always been her morbid fear of being inadequate, particularly regarding her physical appearance and attire. Since her self-assessment depended largely on the judgement of others, most social events and the rituals associated with them such as dressing up in front of mirrors, 'to see and be seen', terrified her. This is made apparent in a number of diary entries such as the one from June 23rd, 1919:

If I hadn't had since midday to settle myself, I should still be twanging and twittering with Garsington. But parties don't fluster me as they used. I don't much care now about the great question of hair; I am resigned to my station among the badly dressed, though the speeding up of my blue dress, and doubts as to its beauty scarcely seem to confirm that statement, However this may be, I enjoyed Garsington saying to myself "The worst moment will be when I come into the drawing room in my blue dress before dinner".⁸⁰

This was an apprehension that never quite left her which is illuminated in another anxious entry from 1935 concerning a dinner party she was invited to. Even in her mid-fifties she was still tremendously concerned about the appropriateness of her dress and

⁷⁸ Cf. Woolf, *Selected Letters*, p. xv.

⁷⁹ Virginia Woolf, *The Waves*, London [et. al.]: Penguin Books, 2000, p. 63.

⁸⁰ Woolf, *The shorter diary*, p. 82.

her appearance in general, even though she was aware that both was quite unnecessary and somewhat ridiculous:

*How terrified I'm getting of Ethel's dressed dinner tomorrow! It makes a kind of ring round my mind. What I'm to wear: my velvet or chiffon: then my hair. When I'm there it'll be as easy as shelling peas – why this apprehension?*⁸¹

These quotations are reminiscent of similar passages in some of her short stories like *The New Dress* which can be said to be partly autobiographical. Just like Virginia Woolf herself, the protagonist is horrified at the idea of being judged by others. Together with her diary entries, this story illuminates that associating with others sometimes put an immense strain on her. Having to gather herself together and readying herself for the “scorching light” of another’s examining gaze was usually a taxing experience for her which she describes in her diary entry from July 21st, 1932, thusly: “*O but I am so tired – [...] how I dry and shrivel: how I lie awake at night longing for rest – this is true. But know that I'm to be pitchforked up into the light and the glare again next day.*”⁸²

At the same time, however, Woolf depended on others to help her create her own identity. It is apparent from many of her letters and diary entries that not only her characters, but also Virginia Woolf herself encountered “*acute difficulty in possessing*”⁸³ themselves. Only in relation to others was she able to establish and maintain a stable sense of self. She expressed this need for affirmation in a letter to Vita Sackville-West in 1926, demanding: “*What I am; I want you to tell me.*”⁸⁴ This notion is re-enforced even further in a letter to Ethel Smyth in 1930 in which Woolf speaks about her incapability of knowing herself and having to ascertain any judgement passed upon her character by way of reflection - either quite literally in a mirror or in other people’s opinions of her:

⁸¹ Woolf, *The shorter diary*, p. 387.

⁸² *Ibid.*, p. 320.

⁸³ George E. Lyon, „Virginia Woolf and the Problem of the Body“, in: *Virginia Woolf: Centennial Essays*, edited by Elaine K. Ginsberg and Laura Moss Gottlieb, introduced by Joanne Trautmann, Troy (New York): The Whitston Publishing Company, 1983, p. 111.

⁸⁴ Woolf, *Selected letters*, p. 201.

*You'd be amused to see how I fret and worry when I am suddenly made aware of my own character. For months I forget all about it, and then someone says But you're the most appalling liar I've ever met, and I rush to the glass (this sheet is a glass) as if I'd been told my dress was upside down, or my nose bleeding. As I told you, I am not a good psychologist.*⁸⁵

This is carried so far that, on the occasion of the death of a friend or acquaintance, Woolf is immediately horror-stricken at how the deaths of close family members and friends would affect the stability of herself. This constructivist approach to identity and selfhood is prevalent not only in her personal life but also as a recurrent theme in her work and is most strikingly realized in the short story *The Lady in the Looking-Glass*.

5.4 Virginia Woolf on character, self and reality in literature

Although she was not in the habit of discussing her writing very frequently or even in much detail in her letters and diaries, several brief statements serve to illuminate her own ideas and intentions with respect to literature in general and her work in particular. As early as 1901, at the age of 19, Woolf states that she dislikes it when characters in fiction lack humanity and seem as though they were “*cut out with a pair of scissors*”⁸⁶. It will still take more than a decade for her to publish her first writings, but here she is already determined that her own characters would be endowed with much richer psychological detail. This desire to make her characters ‘interesting’ is repeatedly uttered in later letters as well, like the one she wrote to Lytton Strachey on February 28th, 1916. In this letter, one can also find a description of how she means to portray reality: “*What I wanted to do was to give the feeling of a vast tumult of life, as various and disorderly as possible, which should be cut short for a moment by the death, and go on again – and the whole was to have a sort of pattern, and be somehow controlled.*”⁸⁷ Again, this quotation reveals her understanding of reality to be shaped by the duality of chaos and randomness on the one hand and the quest for meaning and purpose on the other hand. However, she was keenly aware of the fact that there is no intrinsic meaning

⁸⁵ Ibid., p. 265.

⁸⁶ Woolf, Selected letters, p. 8.

⁸⁷ Ibid., p. 90.

in neither life nor literature and that people will interpret both according to their mental predisposition and their preconceived notions:

*I meant nothing by *The Lighthouse*. One has to have a central line down the middle of the book to hold the design together. I saw that all sorts of feelings would accrue to this, but I refused to think them out, and trusted that people would make it the deposit for their own emotions – which they have done, one thinking it means one thing another.⁸⁸*

Though this was written as an explanation of her novel *To the Lighthouse*, it also applies to her short fiction. Her stories do not convey a handy, ready-made message, but rather serve as projection surface for the reader's own preconceived notions. Our interpretations of them only reflect ourselves back to us. This modernist paradigm of the importance of individual perspective is at the heart of *The Mark on the Wall* which will be discussed in the next chapter of this paper. As many of her works, both fictional and non-fictional, it is centered on the thought process of an individual mind and portrays the world as seen from an inside perspective which ultimately leads to a constructivist view of reality and, implicitly, the self.

⁸⁸ Ibid., p. 228

6. Reality and the self as constructivist entities in

The Mark on the Wall

The Mark on the Wall is one of Virginia Woolf's most experimental stories and the first of her short stories ever to be published. In it "the idea of perceiving the world with an 'innocent eye' reaches its most interesting development".⁸⁹ Naturally, in its anticipation of her great 'stream-of-consciousness' novels such as *Mrs. Dalloway*, *To the Lighthouse* and finally *The Waves*, one could be tempted to dismiss it as a mere apprentice piece or a foreshadowing of later works. However, it is so masterfully crafted in its artistic unity that it deserves appreciation in its own right. In the years preceding the story's publication in 1917, Virginia Woolf had repeatedly been afflicted with various conditions such as anorexia and depression. Having been under the supervision and care of various nurses most of 1915 after a violent fit of madness, she seemed to slowly recover from her ailments during the year of 1916. However, her health and mental stability remained fragile.⁹⁰ As Laura Marcus maintains in *A Shape that Fits*, the short story as a form of artistic growth and expression was best suited for Woolf in that time of her life and career as an author.⁹¹ For one thing, such short publications could easily be handled by the Woolfs' own newly set-up publishing press. Moreover, a short story can be written in one sitting and is therefore less stressful than more extensive projects. It provides an outlet for creative energy and artistic experimentation without the usual "burdens and constraints of plot and character development"⁹² and therefore, without the strain that writing a novel can put on the mind.

The Mark on the Wall is a virtually plotless story. Everything that actually happens on a surface level can be summarized quickly: The main character that is supposedly female sits at the fireplace and contemplates several issues. Her thoughts are interrupted at the end of the story by a person unbeknownst to the reader who informs her that he or she is going to get the newspaper. There is very little action and the 'event' that is narrated seems trifling and hardly worth telling. At the same time, there is a multitude of

⁸⁹ Withworth, 2001, p. 101.

⁹⁰ Woolf, *Short Fiction*, p. xxxix et seq.

⁹¹ Laura Marcus, *Virginia Woolf*, 2nd ed., Tavistock: Northcote House, 2004, p. 18.

⁹² *Ibid.*

thoughts and considerations going on in the protagonist's mind. These mental processes form the actual 'plot' of the story and the rhythm by which the narrative is shaped. The surface level of reality is contrasted with the inner world and provides a frame for the internal musings of this character. By structuring the story in that way, Woolf creates "complex patters of narration which, although specific to each of her novels, are united in combining 'the inner & the outer' and in constructing a relationship between selves"⁹³. Thus, on the one hand, we are presented with a level of reality where very little action is taking place. This might be reality how it presents itself from the perspective of the character who intrudes on the protagonist at the end of the story. On the other hand, there is the reality of the woman who is roaming about in a world of her own. That is probably the reason why she seems to be so confused when she is forced back into that other world of the intruding character: "Where was I? [...] I can't remember a thing. Everything's moving, falling, slipping, vanishing..."⁹⁴ By contrasting the pensive character with the intruding one, Woolf shows how people literally create their own realities in their minds. This "crossover of [...] subjective experience and social reality, is the point of departure for Woolf"⁹⁵ from which she narrates the story. *The Mark on the Wall* works with the 'flight of the mind' technique.⁹⁶ This technique is roughly equivalent to the 'stream of consciousness' technique which is frequently used by modernist writers like Joyce, Faulkner and, of course, Virginia Woolf herself. Both terms refer to the denotation of "the disjointed character of mental processes and the layering and merging of central and peripheral levels of awareness".⁹⁷ This layering of mental processes which is presented in stories like *The Mark on the Wall* substitutes for a traditional plot, because it reflects the motif of several coexisting realities, truths or perspectives much better than a classic story outline could.

The opening passage of the story, though still rather conventionally narrated, provides the first hint at its essential disregard for literary conventions of structure and narration. Without any further information or even establishing the gender or age of the narrator

⁹³ Ibid., p. 27 et seq.

⁹⁴ Woolf, Short Fiction, p 10.

⁹⁵ Skrbic, 2004, p. 34.

⁹⁶ Virginia Woolf, *The Complete Shorter Fiction of Virginia Woolf*, edited by Susan Dick, London: Harvest Book, 1989, p. 4.

⁹⁷ Manfred Jahn, *Narratology: A Guide to the Theory of Narrative. Part 3 of Poems, Plays and Prose: A Guide to the Theory of Literary Genres*, Köln 2002, p. 54.

The Mark on the Wall starts in medias res of the protagonist's silent musings. Interestingly, the entire first paragraph is not yet written in the 'flight of the mind'-technique but features a rather conventional first-person narrator that relates past events in a structured and coherent way. The reader learns of the incident at which the protagonist first noticed the mark on the wall. In these first introductory sentences it is already remarked upon that the mark often serves as a kind of 'safety buoy' the protagonist uses to hoist herself out of her "automatic fancy".⁹⁸ The next paragraph allows the reader a first plunge into the stream of the character's consciousness. The narrative changes from past to present tense and now resembles a free-flowing train of thoughts and associations. Stylistically, this impression is created by the stringing together of several main clauses, subordinate clauses and elliptic sentence fragments. This incoherency is also reflected in the changed typography. Whereas the first paragraph features only full stops, commas and semicolons, the following passage makes frequent use of hyphens, dots and dashes which Woolf obviously believed to more adequately present mental processes in a written form.⁹⁹ In the course of the story, these reverie-like passages become more frequent and elaborate and are only interrupted by silent speculations about the nature of the mark on the wall. Throughout the story an overwhelming sense of immediacy prevails and as the protagonist allows herself to further slip away from the outward reality and into the inner realms of her half-conscious mind, this impression is heightened into a feeling of de-personalization, the image of a dissolving self. These ideas are often what the protagonist considers 'solid' things or 'hard facts'. One longish passage of thought and association, for instance, is interrupted by the character thinking of the clothes she is wearing and the furniture she is sitting on. These thoughts temporarily bring her back to the surface, to "this moment".¹⁰⁰ At another time, it is the thought of Shakespeare or Sunday lunches that functions as temporary point of anchorage in the incessant stream of half-conscious associations. This is remarked upon by Nena Skrbic in *Wild Outbursts of Freedom* when she maintains that "the narrator moves toward the edge of consciousness"¹⁰¹ repeatedly, but, sensing the danger of losing herself, shies away from it and "catches hold of ideas as a safety net".¹⁰² Most important for the shaping of the narrative,

⁹⁸ Woolf, *Short Fiction*, p. 3.

⁹⁹ It is not by chance that the dash is also called 'Gedankenstrich' in German.

¹⁰⁰ Woolf, *Short Fiction*, p. 4.

¹⁰¹ Skrbic, 2004, p. 39.

¹⁰² *Ibid.*

however, is the alternation and interplay of plunging into the depths of the mind and resurfacing again, which takes place in the form of pondering the nature of the mark: “*But as for that mark, I’m not sure about it; I don’t believe it was made by a nail after all. [...] And yet that mark on the wall is not a hole at all. It may even be caused by some round black substance, such as a small rose leaf...*”¹⁰³

Moreover, the style of narration in *The Mark on the Wall* contributes to this impression of a split perspective. Parts of the story are told by a conventional first-person narrator who fulfils all formal criteria: the narrator refers to herself as ‘I’, intrudes into the ‘story’ by making meta-narrative and philosophical comments as well as directly and indirectly addressing the reader. However, in the stream-of-consciousness passages the style of narration doesn’t really fit the conventions of a first-person narrative. Usually, it is the task of a first-person narrator to convey to the reader what goes on in the story. Therefore, that character functions as the narrating ‘I’. In the case of *The Mark on the Wall*, the narrating figure is at the same time a character in the story who is involved in the action and the events that occur. That dimension of the main character is therefore also referred to as ‘experiencing I’. Although Woolf sticks to these narrative conventions by giving at least a basic narrational frame (“*I looked up through the smoke of my cigarette and my eye lodged for a moment upon the burning coals...*”)¹⁰⁴, she subverts the conventions at the same time. She confuses the reader by merging the ‘narrating I’ with the ‘experiencing I’. Although the ‘narrated’ parts are easily recognizable, the reader has the impression that the story is almost entirely unmediated. This is also due to the employment of the ‘flight of the mind’ technique which I’ve mentioned before. It obliterates the boundaries between narrating and experiencing self and tricks us into thinking that what we witness is a virtually unmediated piece of thought. The transition between the one and the other and the blending of the two is rather seamless and smooth and so, in many passages, we fancy overhearing an interior monologue although there is a highly overt narrational voice:

And then I came into the room. They were discussing botany. I said how I’d seen a flower growing on a dust heap on the site of an old house in Kingsway. The seed, I said, must have been sown in the reign of Charles the First. What flowers grew in

¹⁰³ Ibid., p. 4 et seq.

¹⁰⁴ Woolf, Complete Shorter Fiction, p. 83.

*the reign of Charles the First' I asked – (but I don't remember the answer). Tall flowers with purple tassels to them perhaps. And so it goes on.*¹⁰⁵

By playing with the conventions of storytelling, by integrating and subverting them at the same time, Virginia Woolf creates a multi-layered and versatile style of narration which oscillates between traditional structure-dependent forms of narration and the relatively new form of psychological realism. With the narrative structure of *The Mark on the Wall* she dissents from the classical realist dogma that “*art reflects in a straightforward way a single reality*”¹⁰⁶ and instead shows that “*the real is as arbitrary as it is shifting*”.¹⁰⁷ Next to these images of a dissolving self, there are several references to the split of a person into self and image to be found in *The Mark on the Wall*. In the following passage, the protagonist talks about the discrepancy that often exists between our self, as we perceive it and our image, the way others perceive it:

*All the time I'm dressing up the figure of myself in my own mind, lovingly, stealthily, [...]. Indeed, it is curious how instinctively one protects the image of oneself from idolatry or any other handling that could make it ridiculous, or too unlike the original to be believed any longer.*¹⁰⁸

Here, she describes how everybody forms a certain image or idea of the own self, of the person we believe to be or want to be in our minds, how we all construct our own identities and with them our own perspectives on things pertaining to the self. In particular, she remarks upon the fact that everybody would go to great lengths to prevent that self-image from shattering. Had *The Mark on the Wall* not been written that early on in her career, one would be tempted to take it as a meta-fictional comment on her other short stories, since it describes in a nutshell some of the most important themes in Virginia Woolf's works. This passage addresses in a condensed way the problem of the self, its image, the discrepancy between the two and the construction of both. This construction of one's own self is equalled to a reflection in a looking glass. She then lets her protagonist muse on how susceptible this fragile construct really is to

¹⁰⁵ Woolf, *Short Fiction*, p. 5.

¹⁰⁶ *Ibid.*, p. xv.

¹⁰⁷ *Ibid.*

¹⁰⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 5 et seq.

any external influences and disturbances. This is done by employing the metaphor of the shattered mirror, the ‘smashed looking glass’:

*Suppose the looking glass smashes, the image disappears, and the romantic figure [...] is there no longer, but only that shell of a person which is seen by other people [...] As we face each other in omnibuses and underground railways we are looking into the mirror.*¹⁰⁹

In this passage, it is made clear that the way we see ourselves might not necessarily be consistent with the way other people see us. This use of mirror symbolism emphasizes the fact that not even our self is definite, but subject to ‘reflection’. And as well as we are the reflection of our idea about ourselves, we are reflections in other peoples’ looking glasses. Thus, “*there is not one reflection, but an almost infinite number.*”¹¹⁰ At this point, the connection between the mirror image and the motif of a coexistence of realities and identities is rather striking.

Another feature that is worth investigating is wording. The semantics of a text often provide interesting information with regards to its literary content. In *The Mark on the Wall*, the protagonist distinguishes a world of ‘solidity’ and a world beyond the ‘surface’. For her, the mark symbolizes solid reality which she also calls ‘the thing itself, the standard thing, the real thing’. The counterpart to this ‘real thing’ is the world of thoughts in which the protagonist dwells. It is not by accident, that she describes how she came to realize that the ‘thing itself’ does not exist and that “*these real things [...] were not entirely real, were indeed half phantoms*”.¹¹¹ And further on, she reinforces that discovery: “*No, no, nothing is proved, nothing is known.*”¹¹² Although she prefers the quiet little world of her own to the world of hard facts, she is entirely aware that she cannot escape this world for long. Every time she seems to get lost in her thoughts she is brought back to ‘reality’ by the mark on the wall. The topic of different images of the self and the world colliding is taken up again by the wording that is used: “*This train of thought [...] is threatening mere waste of energy, even some collision with reality*”.¹¹³

¹⁰⁹ Ibid.,

¹¹⁰ Susan Dick, *Virginia Woolf*, London: Arnold, 1989, p. 283.

¹¹¹ Woolf, *Short Fiction*, p. 86.

¹¹² Ibid., p. 87.

¹¹³ Ibid., p. 88.

In this choice of words, the modernist assertion that “*reality, including the reality of consciousness, is multidimensional at each instant*”¹¹⁴ comes to the fore on a semantic level.

The motif of colliding views on the self and reality is taken up again in the next story. In *The Legacy* several items, such as a wife’s diaries, and people, such as the parlour maid, serve as mirrors for the deluded protagonist. The apparent clash between what these ‘mirrors’ seem to reflect back to the protagonist and what he chooses to see in them, re-enforces the assumption that Woolf’s concepts of self and reality were essentially of a constructivist nature.

¹¹⁴ John Mepham, *Virginia Woolf*, London: Bristol Classical Press, 1992, p. 55.

7. Modes of auto-perception and hetero-perception in *The Legacy*

The Legacy is a short story first published in the short story collection *A Haunted House and Other Short Stories* in 1943. It is one of Virginia Woolf's less experimental stories. Despite its rather classical structure and form, it provides interesting insights into Woolf's idea of the self by presenting the reader with different modes of perception, namely auto-perception and hetero-perception and the disparity between the two. Furthermore, it illustrates one of Woolf's essential beliefs on fiction itself – that it should present reality, and thus the self, not as absolute entities, but rather as subjectively experienced and interpreted by individuals.

The plot of the story is quickly retold since hardly anything actually 'happens' and the list of dramatis personae is comparatively sparse. One peculiar and important characteristic of *The Legacy* is that it begins shortly after the death of Angela Clandon, one of the two protagonists. We find ourselves in the company of Mr. Gilbert Clandon who is going through the things of his late wife and marvels at finding everything in such perfect order. He wonders as to why she might have left some small gift for every single one of her friends "*as if she had foreseen her death*".¹¹⁵ Not yet grasping the possibility that his wife's death could have been anything but an accident caused by carelessness, his mind soon turns to other things as he waits for Sissy Miller, the parlour maid, to arrive. He means to pass on a brooch his wife had intended for her. He does not seem to find it curious or strange that his wife left him nothing but her diaries and doesn't seem to be overly interested in their content at first. When Sissy Miller finally arrives, he hands over the brooch together with some kind words he has prepared. He naturally takes the dominant position with her and at the end of the conversation condescends to inquire after her plans for the future and assures her that she could depend on his help if she ever needed it. He is somewhat bemused when Sissy Miller extends the same offer to him, in an almost exact repetition of his own words, but quickly finds an explanation for this extraordinary behaviour that suits his disposition.

¹¹⁵ Woolf, *Short Fiction*, p. 93.

He concludes that Sissy Miller must have secretly fancied him all these years. A quick glance at his own reflection in the mirror seems to confirm that interpretation to him as he is still “*as the looking-glass showed him, a very distinguished-looking man*”.¹¹⁶ Amused by this new discovery and inspired by the desire for sharing this excellent ‘joke’ with his wife he turns to her diaries. Corresponding to his wife’s initial admiration for his own person he feels validated in his self-image as an attractive and formidable man. As he reads on his attitude of amusement and mild condescension reveals how much more important and intellectually superior he fancies himself to be compared to his wife. In his thoughts, he characterizes her as a ‘child’ and ‘schoolgirl’ and her life as an “*insignificant trifle*”.¹¹⁷ Consistently, he grows bored as his name appears less often and irritated over the excessive mentioning of someone with the initials B.M., who appears to have been a secret acquaintance. Revealing his self-absorbed and ego-centric personality once again, it upsets him that B.M. had apparently spoken unfavourably of him to Angela. It takes Gilbert Clandon until the very last page of his wife’s diary, her legacy, to realize that B.M. had been her lover. However, he only grasps the full scope of events when Sissy Miller reveals to him on the phone that B.M. was her brother who had killed himself by stepping in front of a car. When it dawns on him that his wife committed suicide to rejoin her lover in death and had left her diary to him as a legacy of truth, he finally understands that his life, his beliefs and his self-image are a delusion.

This brief summary already suggests that *The Legacy* is concerned with how people perceive themselves, how they are perceived by others and the discrepancy that at times exists between the two. This is put to the discerning reader through various means. Firstly, Woolf employs an unreliable focalizer through whose eyes the story is related. Unreliable narrators are often revealed as such immediately by making false or delusional claims which then betray their unreliability. However, in this case Woolf chose the more dramatic way of concealing the focalizer’s unreliability and delusion until the very end of the story. This urges the reader to reconsider his judgement of characters and events. Furthermore, this employment of an unreliable narrator provides a ‘light-bulb moment’ which, in turn, serves to enforce the impression of the fragility of the self and its image. The full scope of the situation is revealed to the reader quite as

¹¹⁶ Woolf, *Short Fiction*, p. 95.

¹¹⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 96 et seq.

unexpectedly as to the protagonist himself as the pretty picture of delusion is shattered with this final realization: “*He had received his legacy. She had told him the truth. She had stepped off the kerb to rejoin her lover. She had stepped off the kerb to escape from him.*”¹¹⁸

Of course, there are hints to the focalizer’s lack of credibility. One can’t help but wonder why his wife leaving everything in such perfect order doesn’t make Gilbert Clandon more suspicious. Furthermore, with his overall demeanour and attitude he reveals himself to be self-absorbed and oblivious to other peoples’ emotions. Thus, he doesn’t strike the reader as someone who is sensitive towards goings-on that do not directly concern his own person. Nevertheless, the element of surprise and with it the cathartic effect is still prevalent at a first reading. Naturally, this changes at a second perusal because the reader is then able to maintain an ironic distance from the protagonist and can knowingly observe the successive deconstruction of his self-image. It then becomes clear that this is done by reflecting the protagonist in mirrors. The most obvious mirror scene takes place when the protagonist is looking at his own reflection in the hallway mirror as if to look for confirmation that his late wife’s parlour maid, Sissy Miller, might very well find him attractive. It is interesting to note the wording Woolf chose for that description: “*He caught his reflection in the glass as he passed. He was over fifty; but he could not help admitting that he was still; as the looking-glass showed him, a very distinguished-looking man.*”¹¹⁹ Rather than using an active phrase such as ‘as he could see in the looking-glass’, the passive wording insinuates that his attractiveness must be an unchallengeable truth and that there cannot possibly be a discrepancy between how he perceives himself and the way others might perceive him. This attitude prevails in the other, more subtle episodes of mirroring. Oblivious to the fact that his self is not a manifestation of an objective truth but subject to interpretation and projection by others, Gilbert Clandon manages to construe each piece of contrary evidence in a way that fits in with his preconceived opinion of himself and keeps missing chances to look at the real image that is reflected back to him, for example, by Sissy Miller. Her obvious embarrassment at the situation he mistakes for simple distress over his wife’s death and her expression of concern for him he misinterprets as a fancy she might have entertained for him all along.

¹¹⁸ Ibid., p. 100.

¹¹⁹ Woolf, Short Fiction, p. 95.

After that chance at undeceiving himself is missed, he proceeds to peruse his late wife's diaries which can be interpreted as a third mirror to different aspects of Gilbert Clandon's personality. Throughout the first several entries, the impression of Mr. Clandon that we garner from his wife's descriptions is predominantly favourable. She comments on his attractive outward appearance as well as his social and professional successes, stating that she is proud to be his wife. This statement is echoed by his own mental assertion of always having been "*very proud to be her husband*".¹²⁰ However, his reason for this sentiment seems to differ vastly from hers. Whereas Angela Clandon appears to sincerely admire her husband's achievements and personal charms, Gilbert Clandon seems to be a lot prouder of himself at having managed to make such a good catch. He seems to regard his wife as a trophy which enhances his own merit and status. That he has little regard for any of her features aside from her beauty is made abundantly clear by calling her "*such a child*"¹²¹. The tone then changes from happiness and admiration to nuances of anxiety, stress and a sense of responsibility and even of guilt at not having borne her husband a child. Again, in his reaction towards his wife's statements the protagonist reveals his own egocentricity. He acknowledges that it must have been a source of pain to his wife to have remained childless, but rather than dwelling on what that could have meant for her, he dismisses it as insignificant since he himself has never regretted it. Indeed, as the story proceeds every single diary entry is commented on in a similarly self-referential fashion. This gives the reader the notion that Gilbert Clandon's purpose in reading these diaries is not commemorating his deceased wife but rather confirming his own greatness as a man and husband. This impression is enforced by the protagonist's admission that as his own name is mentioned less often "*his interest slackened*".¹²² It does not once occur to him that this tendency might only be reflective of having neglected and alienated his wife. He does not seem to make a mental connection between the following entries 'conveying nothing to him' and the sense of complete estrangement his wife must have felt. Only when a character with the initials B. M. is introduced and appears in her entries with increasing frequency his curiosity is aroused once more; even more so when it is made clear that B.M. is a man, a socialist and had apparently made several unfavourable remarks about him to his wife. Again, his interest is mainly sparked by a reference to

¹²⁰ Woolf, Short Fiction, p. 96.

¹²¹ Ibid.

¹²² Ibid., p. 97.

his own person, even if a negative one. It is interesting that this first unfavourable commentary on his character also constitutes the turning point of the story. For the first time subtle notions of doubt begin to insinuate themselves in the mind of Gilbert Clandon as the veil of delusion starts to lift and allows him a glimpse at reality. However, he has not quite disposed of his airs of superiority and condescension yet. His explanation for the growing intimacy in his wife's acquaintance with the mysterious B.M. is that she was simply too ignorant and naïve to see through him. This is made clear when he remarks that she should have talked to him "*instead of puzzling her poor little head about questions that were much too difficult for her to understand*".¹²³ His deliberations take on a tone of desperation, however, as events he can not account for with his limited perspective accumulate. He realizes that B.M. and his wife had been much more intimately acquainted than he could have fathomed and the façade he had fancied to be reality rapidly crumbles away as the truth dawns on him. Not grasping the full scope of repercussions for himself, he remains suspended in uncertainty for a short while until Sissy Miller deals the fatal blow with the four small words of: "*He was my brother*".¹²⁴ At the very end of *The Legacy* we see Gilbert Clandon in the shattered fragments of what was once his personal hall of distorting mirrors. He is finally able to see past these devices of self-deceit and glimpse at the truth that his wife's diaries reflect back to him. As was shown in this analysis, *The Legacy* is a prime example of using mirrors as tropes to reflect ambiguity as well as mirroring techniques as a means of disambiguation.¹²⁵ It also illustrates Woolf's preoccupation with the "*flexible, various or even illusory self*".¹²⁶ This motif is resumed in the following discussion of the short story *Lappin and Lapinova* which focuses on the portrayal and disintegration of the illusory self in an illusory world.

¹²³ Woolf, *Short Fiction*, p. 98.

¹²⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 100.

¹²⁵ For a more detailed account of mirrors as tropes and the usage of mirrors in Woolf's works see the introductory chapter of: Marilyn Kurtz, *Virginia Woolf. Reflections and Reverberations*, New York Peter Lang Publishing Inc., 1990.

¹²⁶ Judy Little, *The experimental self: dialogic subjectivity in Woolf*, Carbondale: Southern Illinois University Press, 1996, p. 29.

8. The illusory self in *Lappin and Lapinova*

Lappin and Lapinova is one of Virginia Woolf's more conventional short stories and is believed to have been written in the late 1930s. Although it does not feature many occurrences of mirror symbolism as such, it takes up the theme of constructing an inner world that differs from outward circumstances and with it a unique perspective that other people do not necessarily share. It also displays how, along with the emergence of this internal world, the protagonist creates new selves for her and her husband in her mind and how these selves are deconstructed throughout the course of the story. Since *Lappin and Lapinova* displays the otherwise prevalent mirror imagery only towards the end of the story, another important level of analysis will be that of semantics. Especially in Woolf's works, the words that are used to narrate a story often hint at a potential underlying concept or idea. In *Lappin and Lapinova*, one of the two main characters, Rosalind, makes up a story of the king rabbit Lappin and his queen hare Lapinova which are to represent her husband Ernest and herself. She creates a world that belongs only to the two of them which she uses to escape from the external demands and obligations that come with marrying into an important family like that of her husband. It is a way of forging a bond by shutting everyone else out: "*Thus when they came back from their honeymoon, they possessed a private world [...] It made them feel, more even than most young married couples, in league together against the rest of the world.*"¹²⁷

Rosalind thinks up this world in every little detail for herself and her husband, because she is unable to cope with the world that the other characters of the story inhabit. This is revealed when she thinks to herself: "*Without that world, how, Rosalind wondered, that winter could she have lived at all?*"¹²⁸ Soon 'that world' becomes her reality and seems to her more real than the world the Thorburns inhabit. Obviously, the term 'world' plays a very important role in the story. It refers to both, Rosalind's dream world and the 'real' world. Of course, the term 'world' can be used interchangeably with the term 'reality', since for the purpose of this thesis both have the same meaning. Moreover, the contrast between the terms 'private world' and 'the rest of the world' and the conflicts

¹²⁷ Woolf, *Short Fiction*, p. 86.

¹²⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 87.

that arise when both collide like in *Lappin and Lapinova* show how important it is to understand that in Woolf's stories there is more than one perspective on reality.

Next to that fundamental modernist theme, *Lappin and Lapinova* also deals with questions of the self, such as whether our background, our heritage or our social role defines our self and whether the self is stable or fluid. This is already hinted at when Rosalind reflects on her new status as a wife. In saying that "*perhaps she would never get used to the fact that she was Mrs Ernest Anybody*"¹²⁹, she acknowledges that with that new social role of being a wife an important aspect is added to her identity, whether she likes it or not. Apart from contemplations about her own destiny, but also in thinking about others, the notion of fixed social roles seems to disturb her. This becomes apparent when she maintains that the name Ernest evokes certain things such as "*the Albert Memorial, mahogany sideboards, steel engravings of the Prince Consort with his family*"¹³⁰, in short everything that symbolizes wealth, tradition and conservatism. As has been mentioned before, that is not a world Rosalind is at home in. To escape from the cognitive dissonance that arises from being married to a man from such a background she invents a new name and identity for him. To her husband, this seems to be simply a game springing from the carefree intimacy of their honeymoon. He plays along, because it seems to make her happy, not realizing that for her it is an issue of fundamental importance. As Hermione Lee has observed, Woolf often broaches the issue of "*the coexistence of different states of mind inhabiting an apparently fixed personality*"¹³¹ and thus implies that "*reality is not fixed*"¹³² which is also a central theme in *Lappin and Lapinova*. Woolf promptly remarks upon this with the assertion that everyone judges a situation "*according to his own circumstances*"¹³³.

Throughout the course of their honeymoon vacation, both protagonists get more deeply involved in this fantasy world. In constructing that alternative realm together, it acquires a tangible quality, especially for Rosalind. That this world of the mind can be just as real as the corporeal world is insinuated by how the protagonists speak of it; for instance, when Ernest speaks of Lapinova, his wife's imaginary counterpart, as the 'real'

¹²⁹ Woolf, *Short Fiction*, p. 84.

¹³⁰ *Ibid.*

¹³¹ Hermione Lee, *The Novels of Virginia Woolf*, New York: Holmes&Meier, 1977, p. 20.

¹³² *Ibid.*

¹³³ Woolf, *Short Fiction*, p. 85.

Rosalind or when it is said that for Rosalind the creatures of her fantasy world become “*very real, very vivid, very amusing*”¹³⁴. Since it is difficult for Rosalind to cope with the reality of having married a Thorburn and the consequences and repercussions that go with it, the fictitious world of hares and rabbits becomes a means of belonging and safety as well as a means of escape. This is strikingly illustrated in the dinner scene where Rosalind feels isolated and overwhelmed at the same time. These feelings are masterfully translated into visual images by Virginia Woolf. She juxtaposes the color gold that is prevalent at the anniversary dinner with the white of Rosalind’s dress. Moreover, this visual contrast is augmented by establishing associative links of sensations with the respective colours. The gold of the dinner party is associated with heat, fire and perspiration, whilst the white of Rosalind’s dress appears in context with the words ‘icicle’ and ‘insoluble’. Clearly, this kind of imagery sets her apart from all the other characters and isolates her from them. At this point, Woolf demonstrates how volatile and unstable Rosalind’s self really is, again making use of the fire and ice imagery. As the dinner progresses, Rosalind is more and more overwhelmed by this foreign world of the Thorburns and feels that she is losing herself in it. This is hinted at when she says that “her icicle was being turned into water”¹³⁵. This image of the dissolving self is emphasized even further in a climatic sequence of three verbs denoting disintegration: “*She was being melted, dispersed; dissolved into nothingness; and would soon faint.*”¹³⁶ Rosalind is ‘rescued’ from that fate by a party guest accidentally mentioning rabbits at which occasion her husband Ernest twitches his nose, which is their secret signal of belonging to each other. Noticing that sign, Rosalind’s perception of the situation undergoes a dramatic change. Where she felt as though she was dissolving and fading just a few sentences before, she now manages to look at things in a friendlier light. In her mind, the dining hall is transformed into a moor, the golden chrysanthemums turn into gorse and the voices of the dinner guests into birdsong. Furthermore, each of the Thorburns is made into something that reveals his or her ‘true’ nature, what they ‘really’ are – a poacher, a ferret and so on. Again, Virginia Woolf shows that reality is often entirely subjective and largely depends on a person’s perspective and interpretation thereof.

¹³⁴ Ibid.

¹³⁵ Ibid., p. 88.

¹³⁶ Ibid.

After the incident at the anniversary dinner, there is a caesura of two years of story time during which husband and wife seem to have somewhat grown apart. Consistently, following the depiction of the construction of their common fantasy world is its deconstruction. With every attempt at communicating, it takes Ernest Thorburn longer and longer to find his way back into his wife's parallel reality. Clearly, their respective perspectives on the world and with it their perceptions of reality have drastically diverged over the course of their marriage. Whereas nothing much changed for Rosalind, Ernest is faced with the harsh reality of having to make a living for both of them and has little time or nerve to indulge in fictional adventures with his wife. This is reflected in her growing anxiety about the true nature of her husband. She starts fearing "*that he was really Ernest; and that she was really married to Ernest*"¹³⁷, which indicates a clash between the image she had entertained of her husband so far and what he seems to have become. Here the essentially modernist question of what the self is, arises once more.

Although mirror symbolism is not quite as pervasive in *Lappin and Lapinova* as it is in some of Woolf's other short stories, there are two significant incidents of mirroring and reflection. The first takes place when we see Rosalind restlessly roaming through the apartment. The doubts about her husband have obviously led her to question her own inner being. Completely disoriented, unsettled and at odds with herself, she seeks consolation and self-confirmation in the looking glass. However, the mirror withholds clarification. Instead of providing her with an answer as to who she really is, the mirror only reflects her anxiety and terror back to her: "*Her joints seemed stiff too, and when she looked in the glass, which she did several times as she wandered about the flat, her eyes seemed to burst out of her head, like currants in a bun.*"¹³⁸ Complementary to that episode, is the closing passage of the story in which Ernest comes home to find his wife in this pitiful state. Other than at the beginning of their marriage, he does not seem disposed to humour her this time. It is made quite clear that the world of Lappin and Lapinova had always been a droll game for him, one of Rosalind's whims that he tolerated because it seemed to make her happy. Now, however he seems determined to put an end to that. When his wife tells him about the terrifying experience of 'loosing

¹³⁷ Woolf, *Short Fiction*, p. 90.

¹³⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 91.

Lapinova', which is tantamount to losing the 'real' Rosalind¹³⁹, he does not attempt to comfort her in any way. Instead, he looks into the mirror straightening his tie. The difference to Rosalind's mirroring episode is immediately obvious – where it withheld a sense of identity for the unsettled self of Rosalind, it confirms Ernest's attitude of confidence. When he coldly asserts that "*poor Lapinova [was] caught in a trap, [...] killed*"¹⁴⁰, it is clear that the mirror does not only serve to reveal two different states of mind, but, by comparison, the irreconcilable rift that is gaping between the two spouses and their views of reality.

The illusory self and its deconstruction is one of the main themes in the *The New Dress* as well. In this story, which will be analyzed in the following chapter, Virginia Woolf uses the mirror symbol to display the protagonist's conflicting self-images and, consequently, the fragility of her identity and self-hood. In contrast to *Lappin and Lapinova*, however, the rift does not occur between two individuals but solely in the heroine's mind.

¹³⁹ Cf. *ibid.*, p. 86: 'Is that what she's called,' said Ernest, 'the real Rosalind?' He looked at her. He felt very much in love with her. 'Yes; that's what she's called,' said Rosalind: 'Lapinova.'

¹⁴⁰ Woolf, *Short Fiction*, p. 92.

9. The unstable self in *The New Dress*

The short story *The New Dress* was published in 1924 whilst Woolf was working on the novel *Mrs. Dalloway*. For that reason, as well as the coincidence of several characters and settings from *Mrs. Dalloway* also making an appearance in *The New Dress*, it seems probable that the story may originally have been one of the chapters of the novel. It is one of Woolf's more conventional 'looking glass' stories and relates the story of Mabel Waring, who is a guest at Clarissa Dalloway's party. In Woolf's works, party-themed passages often revolve around motifs such as rank, social class, fashion and dress, womanhood, judgement and social acceptance. All these themes can be found in *The New Dress* and are directly linked to the use of the mirror symbol. In this story, it is employed for various purposes, one of which is to function as a discerning and judgemental 'public eye' as is suggested by Nena Skrbic in *Wild Outbursts of Freedom*: "Cruelly accenting the division between fantasy and reality, between the contemporary, smart sophistication of the partygoers and Mabel's own garish choice, the mirror functions as a powerful, disciplinary eye."¹⁴¹ *The New Dress* can therefore be interpreted as a story about the limits women face and the artificiality and arbitrariness of these boundaries.¹⁴² Virginia Woolf herself often felt that way about social gatherings and strongly disliked all the procedures they entailed, such as getting dressed in front of a mirror and being judged for her appearance by others. Oftentimes she felt inadequate and exposed on such occasions.¹⁴³ Thus, it is argued by some critics that large parts of *The New Dress* are autobiographical and that not only in the heroine's mind but also for Virginia Woolf herself, mirrors reflect a woman's status and worth which is largely assigned to her by others. It is a very 'personal' story in that it illustrates the 'original sin' of falling from "Edenic unself-consciousness to the agonized knowledge of her own [...] self".¹⁴⁴ This is already made quite clear in the opening passage of the story when Mabel arrives at the party and, as soon as she takes off her cloak and steps into the drawing room, is handed a mirror and is made aware of the several other items such as

¹⁴¹ Skrbic, 2004, p. 68.

¹⁴² Baldwin, 1989, p. 38.

¹⁴³ Cf. Virginia Woolf, *Augenblicke. Skizzierte Erinnerungen*. Aus dem Englischen von Elizabeth Gilbert, Frankfurt a. Main: Fischer, 1998, p. 182 et seq.

¹⁴⁴ Roxanne Fand, *The dialogic self: reconstructing subjectivity in Woolf*, Selingsgrove: Susquehanna University Press, 1999, p. 45.

combs and brushes. This clearly indicates the expectation that women must be of flawless outward appearance to be admitted into society and that they will be ranked according to how well they manage to conform to that expectation. This is further enforced by the way Mabel sees herself and other women in the looking glass as “boot-buttons” or “tadpoles”, as tiny little dots who can only be distinguished by the colour of their dress. Oddly, the other guests by whom Mabel feels snubbed and looked down upon seem to pay much less attention to matters of proper attire or social rank than her. It seems as if Mabel is the only one who is overly concerned with fitting in. She is convinced that she is the target of mockery and that she is disdained by the other guests. Her insecurities prompt thoughts of social and personal inferiority along with the burning desire of being accepted by those who she believes to be superior to her in rank, elegance and taste. However, all of her negative feelings seem to come from Mabel Waring herself, who is deeply insecure and self-conscious. No one in the story comments adversely on her appearance. In fact, several people take note of her new dress and praise it.¹⁴⁵ One of the well-dressed young ladies, for example, tells her that it is “*perfectly charming*”.¹⁴⁶ Rather than simply taking this as a compliment, Mabel suspects that the girl is being insincere and playing her for a fool and remains keenly suspicious of everybody she talks to throughout the party. By regarding all compliments as lies and interpreting all remarks and gestures as criticism, the heroine is the source of her own misery.

Unlike in most of the other stories, the mirror does not serve as a means of revealing a hidden truth or reality, but rather as a catalyst for Mabel’s varying perceptions of her own person. During the course of the story, Mabel sees herself in a looking glass on several different occasions and even though the reflection shows the same person in the same dress, the visions of herself that she perceives are diametrically opposed to one another. These two occasions are the fitting of the dress at the dress maker’s shop and the party itself. On both occasions Mabel Waring sees her reflection in the mirror, wearing the exact same dress. Thus, one would be inclined to think that her perceptions of her outward appearance and the conclusions she draws from it should be rather similar. However, this is not at all the case. When Mabel recalls the scene at Miss

¹⁴⁵ Baldwin, 1989., p. 36 et seq.

¹⁴⁶ Woolf, Complete Shorter Fiction, p. 171.

Milan's workroom where her dress was fitted¹⁴⁷, she remembers seeing a "*mysteriously smiling, charming girl*".¹⁴⁸ She sounds rather satisfied with her outward appearance and the way the dress looks on her. Even at that occasion, however, she does not dare look at herself in the looking glass longer than a few moments. It is almost as though she is afraid that what she is seeing is an illusion which might not withstand a lingering gaze. Consistently, she does not seem to mind when the dressmaker diverts her attention to the length of the skirt. It appears that Mabel is more than content with having been provided with an excuse not to re-examine herself in the mirror. The reason for that lies in her "*deep anxieties about the body and the self*",¹⁴⁹ which is, as previously mentioned, an anxiety that the heroine shares with Virginia Woolf herself. It is the fear that the mirror will reflect an image back at us that is inconsistent with what we had fancied ourselves to look like. Moreover, for Mabel Waring an unfavourable outward appearance is associated with and tantamount to being pathetic and worthless as a person. Thus, her looks are by far not the only thing that looking glasses appear to show her. They seem to reveal aspects of her personality, her character and her worth as a woman and a human being. According to the occasion and the circumstances the assessments vary greatly, even though they seem equally accurate to the heroine at that given point in the story time. It is made quite clear that Mabel does not only see what is there. If that were the case the difference in perceptions would be inexplicable. The discrepancy is easily resolved when one acknowledges that when she gazes into a mirror, she does not see an image of her actual outward appearance but a reflection of her current state of mind that seems to stare back at her. She regards her looks as a "*betrayal of her inner integrity*".¹⁵⁰ Many critics have argued that *The New Dress* is thus a story of self-deceit.¹⁵¹ However, it is not self-deceit of the more common kind where one wishes to remain oblivious to one's own flaws or even one's own virtues. It is deception of a more severe and fundamental nature. The heroine is not capable of forming a consistent judgement on her own character or worth simply because she lacks any "*sense of herself as an adult*".¹⁵² She is unclear as to who or what exactly Mabel Waring might be and thus finds herself at the mercy of the moment. Her own state of

¹⁴⁷ Even though this is related in the story as a flashback, it will be discussed in the chronological order of events, to show the significant disparity between Mabel's visions of her own self, her reality.

¹⁴⁸ Woolf, *Complete Shorter Fiction*, 2006, p. 172.

¹⁴⁹ Skrbic, 2004, p. 68.

¹⁵⁰ Baldwin, 1989, p. 40.

¹⁵¹ Cf. Skrbic 2004.

¹⁵² Skrbic 2004, p. 69.

mind combined with external circumstances dictate the outcome of her self-assessment. As mentioned before, one instance is the fitting of the dress in Miss Milan's workroom. In that scene, the cramped and miserable conditions which Miss Milan is forced to live in make it easy for Mabel to arrive at a favourable judgement of her own person, both through comparison and sympathy. Against the humble surroundings of the dressmaker's room, she stands out and feels "*suffused with light*", "*rid of cares and wrinkles, [...] a beautiful woman.*"¹⁵³ In the light of such a favourable reflection on her looks and personality, Mabel Waring, who is otherwise a rather unsympathetic and self-centered character, even has some consideration and empathy to spare for Miss Milan and her "*miserable, scanty, sordid, little pleasures*".¹⁵⁴ This momentary vision and the sight of Miss Milan kneeling before her busy with adjusting the hem of her dress inspires in Mabel Waring a spirit of all-encompassing love and kindness and even reconciles her with human nature itself. At this point in narrative time the heroine believes this perception to be objectively true and real. She believes she is at that very moment glancing at "*the core of herself, the soul of herself*".¹⁵⁵ However, in offering this self-assessment in the form of a flashback, Woolf contrasts it sharply with how Mabel perceives herself at Clarissa Dalloway's party and, thus, calls her heroine's discernment and the stability of her self-image into question.

As has been hinted at, however, this incident is not related until much later in the story and is embedded into Mabel's party experiences as a flashback. In the opening passage of *The New Dress* the reader is confronted with an entirely different Mabel than that of the dressmaker shop. In the first few lines already, Mabel is portrayed as a timid, fearful, suspicious and self-centered creature. She manages to construe every tiny gesture, every look as a token of disapproval or disdain. Such is her state of mind when she first hurries to observe herself in the looking-glass and, sure enough, this time she assesses herself in an entirely different way. Her appearance and attire are not at all 'right' or what she had perceived them to be at the dress-fitting. Since her fragile self-image is so easily shattered, even this small adversity disconcerts her profoundly. She feels herself immediately beset with feelings of misery, inadequacy and inferiority. Having retreated to a shady corner of the room and not spoken to a single person she already fancies

¹⁵³ Woolf, Complete Shorter Fiction, p. 172.

¹⁵⁴ Ibid.

¹⁵⁵ Ibid.

herself the object of scornful remarks even though there is not a shred of evidence to prove that her suspicions are accurate. Although she had thought the same about her vision of herself in the dressmaker's shop, she now believes that the current self-assessment is the correct one and asserts that the previous judgement had been "*unutterably silly*".¹⁵⁶ It takes little more than Mabel Waring's own insecurity and apprehension about being judged by people whom she believes to be superior in rank, taste and personality to completely turn her self-image around and obliterate any self-confidence she previously felt. Again, Mabel Waring experiences something like an epiphany, a moment of vision like the one in the dressmaker's workroom, only this time under entirely different auspices and resulting in a diametrically opposed assessment of herself and reality: "*She saw the truth. This was true, this drawing-room, this self, and the other false.*"¹⁵⁷ Immediately following this resolute statement, Virginia Woolf provides the reader with the previously discussed memory of the dress-fitting scene. By contrasting these two so strikingly, she undermines the relevance and validity of both and at the same time throws into sharp relief the modernist claim that reality is not objective, that it is "*far from being 'like this'*".¹⁵⁸ Two different visions, two clashing realities, two conflicting selves can seem equally plausible at different points in time. Making masterful use of mirroring and flashback, these passages in *The New Dress* constitute one of Virginia Woolf's best illustrations of the fragile self. This theme is further developed in the scene in which Mabel has a short conversation with Charles, one of the other party guests. In this episode, we find her oscillating between the two interpretations at a rapid rate, trying to hold on to the favourable, optimistic one. She goes from internally accusing her vis-à-vis of being "*malice itself*"¹⁵⁹ to fond memories of Miss Milan which she desperately tries to cling to but is immediately interrupted in that train of thought by suspecting that Charles and another female party guest might be laughing at her. In one last defiant struggle she wonders why she cannot simply hold on to her vision of compassion and kindness before she finally lapses into the self-deprecating, fearful, suspicious version of herself which she cannot escape from for the remainder of the story. The next mirroring episode finds Mabel solitarily sitting on a blue sofa being accosted by Mrs. Holman, another party guest, who apparently wishes to converse with her. This woman, preoccupied with her own daily worries, does not

¹⁵⁶ Woolf, Complete Shorter Fiction, p. 170.

¹⁵⁷ Ibid., p. 172.

¹⁵⁸ Woolf, Modern Fiction, 1972.

¹⁵⁹ Woolf, Complete Shorter Fiction, p. 173.

seem to take any note of Mabel's dress. It does not come as a great surprise that Mabel finds a way of misconstruing this silence as a devaluation of her own person. It almost seems as though she is determined to perpetuate her own agony by finding fault with everything and thus isolating herself from everybody else. Again, her state of mind is reflected in the looking glass. She does not see individual people in it but merely disjointed little dots of different colour. This illustrates her feelings of insignificance and detachedness. She finds it impossible to spare any sympathy for her interlocutor's trials and tribulations and laments this as a general human condition: "*Ah, it was tragic, this greed, this clamour of human beings, like a row of cormorants, barking and flapping their wings for sympathy -- it was tragic, could one have felt it and not merely pretended to feel it!*"¹⁶⁰ This provides an interesting contrast to her previous assessment of human nature in "*its patience and its endurance*"¹⁶¹ at the dressmaker shop. Indeed, the mirror in this passage functions as a 'public eye' under whose merciless gaze Mabel's insecurities run rampant. She keeps peering into it as if trying to find a foothold or confirmation of some description. However, there is nothing to be found – "*the mirror withholds identity and cannot offer a clear definition of personality*".¹⁶² She is looking in the wrong place.

In the next long passage, the illustration of Mabel's war with her self-image is carried to an extreme. She dwells on her past, blaming her wretchedness and insecurity on her family background characterizing it as mediocre and unspectacular. Also, she regrets having married that same kind of man and having given up her dreams of romance and adventure, the fantastic hope of acquiring for her life and herself importance and meaning. Her mood then swings in the opposite direction, and she recalls moments in which she felt at peace with herself, others and the world such as sitting by the sea or cutting up meat for a Sunday lunch. However, deliberations of that nature do not prevail for long before she concludes that such moments have always been sparse for her and will for some obscure reason occur even less frequently the older she gets. From there it is only a small step to self-accusatory thoughts and self-deprecation. Consistently, one after another she begins to challenge and discredit everything in her life beginning with denouncing herself as an "*unsatisfactory mother*" and "*wobbly wife*" and describing

¹⁶⁰ Woolf, Complete Shorter Fiction, p. 174.

¹⁶¹ Ibid., p. 172.

¹⁶² Skrbic, 2004, p. 71.

her entire family as being “*poor, water-veined creatures who did nothing*”.¹⁶³ Eventually, she comes to the decision that she will have to transform herself into a new person. She intends to shake the habit of fretting about other people’s opinion of her and maintains that she will enjoy life and be at peace with herself, regardless of what anyone might think of her attire. She then decides to step out of the discerning eye of the public. This is illustrated by her stepping out of the range of the various looking glasses that she had been reflected in throughout the entire story:

*So she got up from the blue sofa, and the yellow button in the looking-glass got up too, and she waved her hand to Charles and Rose to show them she did not depend on them one scrap, and the yellow button moved out of the looking-glass...*¹⁶⁴

She takes her leave and tries to say her goodbyes gracefully. However, as she makes her way downstairs to the drawing room, her resolve wavers again for one last time. Mabel Waring has lost this last battle in her on-going war with her self-image and will remain the cringing, fearful creature the reader was introduced to at the onset of the story.

The New Dress illustrates the battle between an everyday version and an ideal version of oneself; a version that is not completely illusionary since it does flicker into being sporadically. Therefore, contrary to stories like *The Legacy*, the main theme in *The New Dress* is not one of illusion and subsequent objectification. The looking glasses rather act as a visualization of a violent inner conflict between two versions of the self. What they reflect is a projection of the self that has respectively gained the upper hand in the protagonist at any given time she looks into the mirror. The mirrors show representations of different states of mind and self-projections and point to hidden personality layers. Thus, *The New Dress* is not primarily a story of shattered illusions, although this is reminiscent as part of the main theme, but rather a tale of being at strife with oneself.

¹⁶³ Woolf, Complete Shorter Fiction, 2006, p. 176

¹⁶⁴ Ibid.

10. Capturing the essence of life in fiction: *The Lady in the Looking-Glass*

The Lady in the Looking-Glass was written in 1929 and is one of Woolf's most interesting looking-glass stories, both in structure and motif. Thematically, it alludes to *The New Dress*, since both stories display conflicting, even diametrically opposed images of a heroine through the employment of several mirroring episodes. Yet, the narrational techniques differ dramatically which makes for an interesting contrast. Both are typically modernist short stories and as such are narrated from the inside out. Whereas in *The New Dress* Mabel Waring serves as a focalizer, it is much more difficult to determine from whose point of view *The Lady in the Looking-Glass* is narrated, which accounts for much of the story's mysterious charm. Stylistically, *The Lady in the Looking-Glass* is a hybrid form making use of more conventional techniques of narration as in *The Legacy*, as well as featuring some 'stream-of-consciousness' elements that can also be found in her earlier stories like *Kew Gardens* or *The Mark on the Wall*, the latter of which might be the most suitable comparison. Amongst the body of her short fiction, it is also the story which makes the most extensive use of mirror symbolism and examines topics like perception, identity and the self most profoundly. All these essentially modernist themes are masterfully incorporated into *The Lady in the Looking-Glass*.

Not unlike *The Mark on the Wall* and a few of Woolf's other more experimental stories, *The Lady in the Looking-glass* is virtually plotless. On a surface level, hardly anything seems to have transpired when the reader and the narrator arrive at the end of the story. These superficial 'events' can be summarized in a very few words. A woman by the name of Isabella Tyson takes a stroll in her garden while a man delivers her mail. She then returns to the house to find the letters on her drawing table at the end of the story. Now, similarly to *The Mark on the Wall* this sketchy plot only presents the fountain that breaks through the surface while the rest of the story takes the reader on a dive into the deep waters of consciousness. What is intriguing about *The Lady in the Looking-Glass* is the way it is narrated. The only actual character in the story is Isabella Tyson. However, she does not have a voice of her own. Instead, she is only a reverberation in

the mind of the narrator. There are very few clues as to who this narrator figure might be. From the point of view and perspective one can infer that the narrating "I" and the narrated "I" are not identical. The voice is that of an external observer, a perceiver of what is reflected in the looking glass which is hanging in the drawing room. There are several allusions to the fact that the narrator is prying on the character in the story. This is already indicated by the first sentence where it is said that "*people should not leave looking-glasses hanging in their rooms*"¹⁶⁵ for the reason that "*one could not help looking*"¹⁶⁶. The reader is made aware that the narrating voice is an intruding presence attempting to prize from Isabella Tyson all her secrets and to reveal her innermost being. Interestingly, the narrator's perspective seems to be confined to the drawing room and the range of the mirror's reflections. It appears that "*outside the disciplined confinement of its frame*"¹⁶⁷ the narrator must rely on the imagination. Curiously, it is said in a later section of the story, that "*under the stress of thinking about Isabella, her room became more shadowy and symbolic*"¹⁶⁸. This statement suggests that there is not actually another person in the room who provides the reader with his or her perceptions, but that the narrative consists of the contents and goings-on of the drawing room related as though it was a human mind. The point of departure for this sort of narration is the question of how her surroundings perceive Isabella Tyson. The drawing room in *The Lady in the Looking-Glass* serves as a symbol for the outside that is attempting to catch a glimpse into the inside. By narrating the story in this way, Virginia Woolf focuses the attention on the issue of identity and perspective. She stresses the dichotomy between the self and the other whilst also pointing to the fact that both are interlinked. Thus, it is easy to see why this narrative voice has no other option then to revert to speculative reveries until Isabella Tyson becomes visible in the mirror at the end of the story. The reader, of course, is not immediately aware that these thoughts are mere speculation until the truth is revealed in the last passage of the story. This meandering of the mind also presents the organizing principle of *The Lady in the Looking-Glass*. There are long passages of internal musings which are evoked by tiny distractions, such as someone bringing in the mail, some outward object that happens to engage the narrator's attention or simply an idea that emerges in the mind. Each of these distractions directs

¹⁶⁵ Woolf, Virginia, Short Fiction, p. 63.

¹⁶⁶ Ibid.

¹⁶⁷ Skrbic, 2004, p. 76.

¹⁶⁸ Woolf, Short Fiction, p. 65.

the narrator's thoughts onto a new path that is then ardently pursued and in turn prompts renewed deliberations on the person of Isabella Tyson.

The opening passages, next to the warning about the revealing nature of looking glasses, contain a description of the scene and its reflection in this particular mirror. In this passage, there is an interesting disparity in the depiction of what happens in the room itself, what is consequently related to the reader and what is reflected in the mirror. The room itself is described as "*full of such shy creatures, lights and shadows, curtains blowing, petals falling*"¹⁶⁹ whereas the reflection of the room in the mirror seems to transfix everything to its spot. Woolf here emphasizes the stark contrast between the reality "*of the transient and the perishing*"¹⁷⁰, on the one hand, and the "*trance of immortality*"¹⁷¹, on the other hand. An interesting interpretation of this deliberate discrepancy can be found in *Wahrnehmung und Perspektivik* by Gudrun Rogge-Wiest, where it is suggested that the contrast between the transience of the room itself and the transfixedness of the image in the looking glass can be taken as metaphors for reality and the arts.¹⁷² Indeed, it is not unlike Woolf to incorporate such subtle meta-fictional commentary into her works. Moreover, the mirror is not only a suitable symbol for literature or the arts in general but also provides an apt analogy for this story in particular. In attempting to capture the true essence of its protagonist it can never transcend the boundaries of fiction and will essentially always remain an artificial representation.

The principal 'character' of the story, Isabella Tyson, is not introduced to the reader any earlier than in the opening sentence of the fourth paragraph which re-enforces the impression that *The Lady in the Looking-Glass* is not primarily concerned with relating the story of a protagonist but rather an exploration of reality, reflections, perceptions and identity. Consistently, in that introductory sentence there is already an allusion to the looking glass to be found. The narrative voice recalls the reflection of Isabella Tyson that was visible in the mirror half an hour ago "*in her thin summer dress,*

¹⁶⁹ Ibid., p. 63.

¹⁷⁰ Ibid., p. 64.

¹⁷¹ Ibid.

¹⁷² Gudrun Rogge-Wiest, *Wahrnehmung und Perspektivik in ausgewählten Romanen Virginia Woolfs*, Frankfurt a. M.: Lang, 1999, p. 6.

carrying a basket".¹⁷³ Up to the very end of the story, these will remain the only actual facts the reader is provided with since by "*stepping out of the gilt rim of the looking-glass*"¹⁷⁴, the protagonist eludes the narrator's scrutinizing glance. This absence prompts the narrator's trance-like speculations and the first venture point for these internal assumptions are the flowers Isabella Tyson supposedly went to pick. In this passage the narrator attempts to guess what kind of flower Isabella Tyson might prefer and what this choice would reveal about her character. Displeased with this analogy, the narrative voice announces that it is a shame to know so little about a person as to have to resort to such comparisons. At the same time, the narrator asserts that "*there must be truth*".¹⁷⁵ Realizing how little one truly grasps of the essence of another human being in general and of Isabella Tyson in particular, the narrator attempts to pin down the truth with the help of facts:

*As for facts, it was a fact that she was a spinster; that she was rich; that she had bought this house and collected with her own hands [...] the rugs, the chairs, the cabinets which now lived their nocturnal life before one's eyes.*¹⁷⁶

This passage contains several modernist topics that resonate throughout Woolf's work. The theme of reality being composed of at least two distinct layers is prominently featured in this part of the story. Woolf had made a very similar distinction between the level of 'hard facts' and the transient flux underneath this surface level in short stories like *The Mark on the Wall* or novels like *To the Lighthouse*. This is emphasized by the employment of the dichotomy between the actual room and the reflection where "*the facts, the reality of the story, remain fixed in the reflection of the mirror, and the truths of time and space are ignored by the imaginative assumptions of the narrative*".¹⁷⁷ Similarly, Woolf's preoccupation with the question of whether it is possible to know another person to his/her core comes to the fore here. This quest for a foothold, the casting about for clues that is so characteristic for the way *The Lady in the Looking-Glass* is narrated, represents the way most human beings deal with an uncertain

¹⁷³ Woolf, *Short Fiction*, p. 64.

¹⁷⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁷⁵ *Ibid.*

¹⁷⁶ *Ibid.*

¹⁷⁷ Skrbic, 2004, p. 76.

situation or reality. They grasp at the hard facts and interpret them from their personal perspectives. This is exactly the prevalent organising principle of the next passages in *The Lady in the Looking-Glass*. From the existence of letters in her desk drawers it is inferred that she must have had an eventful past with many friends, enemies and lovers and her indifferent face prompts the assumption that she simply keeps her emotions walled up behind a stony façade.

As Dean Baldwin maintains in *Virginia Woolf: A Study of the Short Fiction*, this train of thought is “*plausible and interesting enough, but there is no way to verify it*”.¹⁷⁸ Consequently, these deliberations are abandoned as soon as something tangible takes place which in this case, is a man bringing in the mail. The choice of words here is remarkable. The narrative voice’s ‘reflections’ are suspended by the arrival of a person who disturbs the still-life image in the mirror. The artificial vision is intruded upon by reality and is subsequently referred to as “*unrecognisable and irrational and entirely out of focus*”¹⁷⁹. This description much resembles a consciousness that is abruptly forced back to the surface level of reality, into a dismayed fluster and only gradually settles back into a quieter flow of thoughts and associations. Along with that process of sinking back into the quieter realms of the psyche, the letters are “*made part of the picture and granted that stillness and immortality which the looking-glass conferred*”¹⁸⁰. Again, this statement appears to emphasize the dichotomy not only of two levels of reality but also to the fact that the mirror serves as a symbol for consciousness. Everything takes place within the mirror just as everything takes place within the mind. There is no reality outside or separate from the mind’s subjective perceptions and interpretations. This is made clear in the following passage where the narrative voice’s attempts to know the truth about Isabella Tyson become increasingly more aggressive: “*Isabella did not wish to be known – but she could no longer escape. It was absurd, it was monstrous. If she concealed so much and knew so much one must pry her open [...].*”¹⁸¹

As there are no further clues to guide the quest for truth, the narrator now resorts to the imagination as a means of exploring the true nature of its host. However, this endeavour

¹⁷⁸ Baldwin, 1989, p. 56.

¹⁷⁹ Woolf, Short Fiction, p. 65.

¹⁸⁰ Ibid.

¹⁸¹ Ibid., p. 66.

is of very little avail. The enigmatic lady's mind withstands the persistent mental probing. The narrator fails in penetrating her smooth, seemingly indifferent, stony façade. The unaided imagination reaches no further than her expressionless exterior that eludes any attempt at interpretation:

*The sun would beat down on her face, into her eyes; but no, at the critical moment a veil of cloud covered the sun, making the expression of her eyes doubtful – was it mocking or tender, brilliant or dull? One could only see the indeterminate outline of her rather faded, fine face looking at the sky.*¹⁸²

As is often the case in Virginia Woolf's short stories, the semantics of the text's diction point to its content. Words such as 'veil', 'cloud', 'doubtful', 'indeterminate' and 'faded' denote the impenetrability and obscurity of Isabella Tyson's character as well as indicating the uncertainty that results from these notions. It becomes apparent that unaided imagination is not a sufficient tool for capturing the "*profounder states of being*".¹⁸³ Here, Woolf subtly raises the question of whether one mind can ever completely know and understand another mind, whether the desire for seeing a person the way they 'really' are can be sated or whether one is forever destined to perceive things through the distorting lens of personal experience and perspective. Despite Woolf's and her characters' apparent desire for unity and oneness, her stories usually emphasize the plurality of perspectives through which Woolf attempts to explore and understand the different aspects of reality.¹⁸⁴

In the following passage, again, there is an overwhelming sense of a desire to infiltrate Isabella Tyson's mind, to "*penetrate a little farther into her being*"¹⁸⁵, as it were. This type of 'prying' alludes to the conventional realist approach to narration in which the character is typically treated rather 'roughly', as though it were a fixed entity. However, this approach does not satisfy in the modernist short story, as the narrative voice implies when it states that one could not simply pry the character open "*as if she were an oyster*".¹⁸⁶ In this sentence, the narrator realizes that a person is much deeper than

¹⁸² Ibid.

¹⁸³ Ibid.

¹⁸⁴ Cordula Lemke, *Wandel in der Erfahrung: die Konstruktion von Welt in den Romanen von Virginia Woolf und Jeanette Winterson*, Trier: WVT, 2004, p. 167.

¹⁸⁵ Woolf, *Short Fiction*, p. 67.

¹⁸⁶ Ibid.

originally believed and that one must look for more subtle ways to fathom the core of her being. Subsequently, due to a lack of actual events to observe, the narrator relapses into a cascade of uncurbed associations, guessing at the thoughts that might go through the enigmatic lady's head. At this point, the reader needs to be careful not to misconstrue these speculations as fact and to keep in mind that they are merely attributed to the mind in question. That all these descriptions about cutting flowers and standing in the sun thinking about strawberry nets and life and death are figments of the narrator's imagination, becomes apparent when suddenly, at the end of this section, the narrator dryly comments that "*here was she in the looking-glass*"¹⁸⁷. Hence, the reader is made aware that the previous commentary must have been a figment of the imagination since the perspective has been restricted to the drawing room and the range of the mirror and thus, cannot possibly have commented on actual events that took place in the garden. The subsequent mirroring episode itself can be divided into two distinct passages – Isabella Tyson approaching the mirror on the one hand and her being fully visible in it at the very end of the story on the other hand. This is indeed the only passage in the story where the title *The Lady in the Looking-Glass* is justified as the reader is not provided with an actual reflection of her in the mirror before that. Eventually, the much-anticipated final objectifying act of mirroring is about to take place. Before the last veil of ignorance is pulled to the side however, Woolf describes the character's gradual approach as the reflection of her walking up the garden path towards the house can be seen in the mirror. Naturally, this passage is meant to increase the feeling of anticipation before the final revelation, but it can also be interpreted as an interesting allegory. If one takes the suggestion of the mirror symbolizing the arts into consideration, the allegory emerges quite clearly. What Woolf describes here is the gradual absorption of real life into fiction, the transformation of the uncertain and transient into a fixed and immovable piece of literature. The gradual emergence of the mysterious lady's figure in the looking glass can be taken to symbolize the process of fixation and fictionalization real events and people undergo to become 'stories' and characters in stories: "*And all the time she became larger and larger in the looking-glass, more and more completely the person into whose mind one had been trying to penetrate.*"¹⁸⁸ As the figures in a narrative are shaped, the author must decide how to portray them. Thus, they are moulded into their literary form. This process is alluded to

¹⁸⁷ Ibid.

¹⁸⁸ Ibid.

when the narrative voice asserts that “one verified her by degrees – fitted the qualities one had discovered into this visible body”¹⁸⁹. Gradually, all these different qualities are incorporated into the story as the lady is incorporated into the image in the mirror: “And the letters and the table and the grass walk and the sunflowers which had been waiting in the looking-glass separated and opened out so that she might be received among them.”¹⁹⁰ However, in this passage nothing is said about Isabella Tyson except for a brief mentioning of some of her outward features and her clothing. As long as she is not right in front of the mirror, the reader and the narrative voice are likewise unable to penetrate her exterior. “Until fact and imagination are unified into a stable work of art the subject remains elusive, changing, quixotic”¹⁹¹, as is suggested in *A Study of the Short Fiction*. The objectification of the enigmatic lady’s true nature is only accomplished in the very last scene in which her reflection fills the frame of the mirror completely.

In this final scene, the truth about Isabella Tyson is eventually revealed without mercy. As in a few of the previously analyzed stories like *The Legacy*, the looking-glass in *The Lady in the Looking-Glass* acts as a “cruel usurper of illusion”¹⁹² which exposes the narrator’s commentary as mere speculation and calls into question any notions the reader might have entertained of Isabella Tyson so far. It is not the case that the mere event of the character being reflected brings about the unravelling of the mystery, but that the mirror itself plays an active role in tearing down the façade which is strikingly illustrated by Woolf with the use of rather violent imagery: “At once the looking-glass began to pour over her a light that seemed to fix her; that seemed like some acid to bite off the unessential and superficial and to leave only the truth.”¹⁹³ Again, the analogy with the preferred depiction of a character in modernist literature is quite striking. The mirror strips her of all veils and adornments, whether corporeal or imaginative, and presents to the reader the true essence of its reflected object – “the woman herself”.¹⁹⁴ Outward appearance and dress are disregarded in this unsparing portrayal of a human being. This is symbolized by the “pitiless light”¹⁹⁵ that is unleashed on the protagonist

¹⁸⁹ Ibid.

¹⁹⁰ Ibid., p. 68.

¹⁹¹ Baldwin, 1989, p. 56.

¹⁹² Skrbic, 2004, p. 79.

¹⁹³ Woolf, *Short Fiction*, p. 68.

¹⁹⁴ Ibid.

¹⁹⁵ Ibid.

by the looking glass. What is eventually revealed to narrative voice and reader alike is a horrifying vision of nothingness and emptiness: “*She stood naked in that pitiless light. And there was nothing. Isabella was perfectly empty. She had no thoughts. She had no friends. She cared for nobody.*”¹⁹⁶ These words provide one of the harshest displays of a clash of realities in Virginia Woolf’s works with which she asserts that our perception of the truth depends entirely on our perspective on and preconception of reality. Ultimately, the reader is not provided with incontestable truth that this vision is an accurate judgement of Isabella Tyson. Whether that final revelation is *the* truth about her, or *a* truth remains for each individual reader to ponder. Of course, this stripping down of the character is an astute description of what modernist writers have strived to achieve in their works. Thus, *The Lady in the Looking-Glass* is an apt allegory for the modernist ambition to penetrate the minds of their literary subjects, to roam their inner worlds and to capture their true essence. Whereas daily life in its transience and constant change may not be able to extract such truths, the arts in general and literature in particular are more suitable mediums if one wishes to squeeze out of the bones of reality the marrow of truth. If one was to extract a message from *The Lady in the Looking-Glass* it might be that only the written word can compose, transfix and explore an object in such a way whereas in real life truth will always remain multi-faceted and “*inescapably perspectival*”.¹⁹⁷

All aspects of selfhood and identity, image and perception, the real world and the world of the mind that came to the fore in *The Lady in the Looking-Glass* as well as in the stories analysed so far, are merged into one modernist masterpiece in the novel *The Waves* which can be regarded as Woolf’s ultimate manifest on issues of the self and the other and will be examined in greater detail in the following chapter.

¹⁹⁶ Ibid.

¹⁹⁷ Howard Harper, *Between Language and Silence. The Novels of Virginia Woolf*, Baton Rouge: Louisiana State University Press, 1982, p. 3.

11. Self-effacement and self-affirmation in *The Waves*

The Waves, which was published in 1931, is the culmination of Virginia Woolf's experimental stream-of-consciousness prose and is regarded as her masterpiece, by many critics and readers alike. It is the last and the most radical of her psychological novels in its structure, style of narration and depiction of character and is, thus, considered one of the most innovative, but also most inaccessible modernist novels. Similarly to some of her earlier short stories like *The Mark on the Wall*, it explores the inner workings of its characters. This exploration takes place in so-called 'dramatic soliloquies' (also known as sustained interior monologue) which "undertake to reproduce, without a narrator's intervention, the full spectrum and continuous flow of a character's mental process"¹⁹⁸. However, the six characters are not depicted through direct conversation or action. They do not speak or communicate with one another in a literal sense but rather commit acts of self-presentation and self-assertion. This produces an effect almost "like that of a photographic negative, in which what is 'said' by the characters is actually what they think or feel, while their actual speech remains out of earshot"¹⁹⁹. The artificiality of this technique, of course, is evident from the opening pages by the excessive use of the inquit formula. For the purpose of this paper, *The Waves* provides an interesting object of study, since it is preoccupied with questions of selfhood and self-effacement much more than any of Virginia Woolf's other novels. The inherently modernist topic of the dichotomy between individuality and unity is especially emphasized in this work and creates the impression that those are questions that Woolf herself regarded as central to her life as an author and a woman. In that way, despite the impersonality of its prose, it can be taken as one of her most personal books. As Kate Flint puts it in her introduction to the Penguin Classics edition of *The Waves*, it is an "investigation of her own patterns of thought, particularly when faced with the problem of understanding the nature of identity"²⁰⁰. This quest for the nature of identity presents itself in the portrayal of the six characters of *The Waves* – Bernhard, Louis and Neville as the male protagonists on the one hand and Jinny, Susan and Rhoda as their

¹⁹⁸ Abrams, 1999, p. 299.

¹⁹⁹ Julia Briggs, *Virginia Woolf: An Inner Life*, London [et. al.]: Penguin Books, 2006, p. 238.

²⁰⁰ Kate Flint, *Introduction to The Waves*, in: Woolf, Virginia, *The Waves*, London [et. al.]: Penguin Books, 2000, p. x.

female counterparts. Whilst attempting to determine whether the six voices are distinct characters or simply different aspects of the same consciousness, the reader is already deeply immersed into the structural complexity of this novel as there are clues that support either of these assumptions. For instance, between the six voices there exists a superficial diversity that is indicated by their different names, their respective genders as well as the divergence in their preferred imagery. Simultaneously, however, there is also a striking sameness of voices. As the children grow up in the course of the novel, for example, no idiosyncratic adaptations to age, gender role or assumed character traits become apparent. The six voices speak the same way as children as they speak as adults and the idiom of the female characters does not differ significantly from that of the male characters. Moreover, some of the characters draw on the same body of images repeatedly. This consistency of style and tone hints at the underlying equivalence of the characters. Yet, an intricate web of relationships is created between the characters through differences, correspondences and recurrences while at the same time the voices seem to be part of one medium or merged into one observant spirit. In summary, it could be asserted that even though the boundaries between the individual minds tend to blur throughout the text, these temporary events of merging do not entirely obliterate the individuality of the characters.²⁰¹ As Flint put it, the novel dramatizes “*how identities themselves do not stand ultimately, clear and distinct, but flow and merge into each other*”²⁰². This way of portraying characters indicates that Woolf means to play with notions of unity and individuality, of self-assertion and self-effacement. This is alluded to by the character of Bernhard when he says: “*Who am I? I have been talking of Bernhard, Neville, Jinny, Susan, Rhoda and Louis. Who am I? Am I all of them? Am I one and distinct?*”²⁰³ Out of the six voices, Bernhard is the narrator who provides a framework for the impersonal ever-flowing prose and loosely holds the threads together. It is his function to make the reader aware of the existence of these “*divisions between the self and the other*”²⁰⁴ which can be considered the central theme of the novel. As is to be expected from the preoccupation with such topics, the novel also features some occurrences of mirror symbolism. In *The Waves*, the mirror imagery is predominantly associated with the link between the body and its reflection and the self. Interestingly

²⁰¹ Cf. Elfi Bettinger, *Das umkämpfte Bild. Zur Metapher bei Virginia Woolf*, Stuttgart [et. al.]: Metzler, 1993, p. 194.

²⁰² Flint, 2000, p. xi.

²⁰³ Woolf, Virginia, *The Waves*, p. 222.

²⁰⁴ Flint, 2000, p. xxiv et seq.

enough, the two characters that are concerned with this the most are both female – Rhoda and Jinny. This might be an allusion to Woolf’s own traumatic experiences and the resulting problematic attitude towards her body and its reflection in the mirror. The most striking example and at the same time the most problematic character with respect to these issues is, undoubtedly, Rhoda. Out of the six characters in *The Waves*, Rhoda is the most fragile, anxious and sensitive one. Moreover, she lacks any sense of selfhood or identity and is incapable of experiencing herself as a discrete entity which makes daily life unbearable for her. Whereas the other characters assert their own identity and act according to their individual traits, needs, and desires, Rhoda must “*look first and do what other people do when they have done it*”²⁰⁵. She is not able to act out her own self and must rely on others around her whose behaviour she can copy. Of course, that is not a very feasible solution for a longer period of time, and she soon realizes that she will have to “*put off my hopeless desire to be Susan, to be Jinny*”.²⁰⁶ These tendencies become all the more apparent when all six characters outgrow childhood and with it the blissful state of being oblivious to oneself. While the other five voices develop unique idioms and distinctive personalities, Rhoda is busy struggling not to lose herself. All characters in *The Waves* are defined by the contrasting paradigms of unity and individuality and gravitate towards the one or the other in the course of the novel. Rhoda, however, is located on the far end of the scale of self-effacement. She is unable to assert her existence in the material world without touching something corporeal which is depicted in her attempts to master her fears of ‘sinking’ and ‘dissolving’ and temporarily assuring herself by touching a brick wall in the street or the rail of her bed. Only by physical contact, Rhoda is enabled to perceive that her body is different from the material world around her. Thus, it is only consistent that Rhoda is horrified by the idea of looking at herself in the mirror. Since she is so estranged from her own body, seeing her face in a mirror presents a terrifying challenge which she tries to avoid at all costs: “*That is my face,*” said Rhoda, *‘in the looking-glass behind Susan’s shoulder – that face is my face. But I will duck behind her to hide it, for I am not here. I have no face.’*”²⁰⁷ Naturally, looking into a mirror would force Rhoda to confront the question of who she is. Rhoda experiences herself as fragmented, as “*broken into separate pieces*”

²⁰⁵ Woolf, *The Waves*, p. 31.

²⁰⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 19.

²⁰⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 30.

²⁰⁸ and not as a whole, coherent self. In contrast to the other characters, which constantly ponder, question and develop their sense of identity, Rhoda simply refuses to acknowledge that she, in fact, is a self. That is why the phrase of ‘I have no face’ becomes a mantra that she repeats over and over. For her, it is nearly impossible to establish the borders of her mental and physical self ²⁰⁹ without the crutches of touching or imitating. Seeing a coherent reflection of herself in the mirror, therefore, would expose her to the pressure of acknowledging and interpreting her appearance and herself. Thus, it would create significant cognitive dissonance, which Rhoda is not prepared to ‘face’, both figuratively and literally. In Rhoda’s case, the look into the mirror stands for the modern “*loneliness of self-estrangement*” ²¹⁰. Her terror at this moment of self-recognition and self-confirmation is an echo of feelings of uncertainty and anxiety that accompanied the diversification of social roles and concepts of selfhood and identity which had set in at the beginning of modernism. In the figure of Rhoda, this notion is carried to an extreme which becomes apparent when she cannot even cross a puddle of water on the street without feeling that her identity is being assailed. In contrast to the other voices, she is unable to sustain her sense of self from one moment to another: “*I am afraid of the shock of sensation that leaps upon me, because I cannot deal with it as you do – I cannot make one moment merge in the next.*” ²¹¹ The logical consequence of Rhoda’s natural disposition and the daily agony that results from it is her desire to escape from the conscious, real world and therefore it does not come as a surprise when it is succinctly announced that she committed suicide towards the end of the novel. In literary terms, her suicide can be seen as the ultimate effacement, the final merging of the consciousness with the unifying spirit, as well as a “*return to infancy, to the undifferentiated body*” ²¹² and mind.

The second character who is frequently associated with mirror imagery in *The Waves* is Jinny. In many ways, Jinny and Rhoda present two extremes of one scale. Their characters are diametrically opposed – whereas Rhoda lacks any sense of self-hood and wishes to be absorbed into nothingness, Jinny is extremely aware and assertive of her identity and guards her individuality viciously. In contrast to Rhoda, who is entirely out

²⁰⁸ Ibid., p. 79

²⁰⁹ Cf. Gabriele Schwab, *Entgrenzungen und Entgrenzungsmymthen: zur Subjektivität im modernen Roman*, Stuttgart: F. Steiner Verlag Wiesbaden, 1987, p. 95.

²¹⁰ Kurtz, 1990, p. 126.

²¹¹ Woolf, *The Waves*, p. 97.

²¹² Flint, 2000, p. xxxiii.

of touch with her physical existence, Jinny is “*preoccupied by her own body and its surface and its sensations*”²¹³ to an extent where she perceives and understands the world and other people primarily in terms of the body rather than the mind. Thus, she is prone to live in the moment as is indicated even at the beginning of the novel: “*This is only here; this is only now. Now we lie under the currant bushes and every time the breeze stirs we are mottled all over.*”²¹⁴ As opposed to Rhoda, Jinny is capable of living from moment to moment since her self-boundaries are very stable. Already as an adolescent, Jinny is keen on seeing herself in the mirror. In contrast to Rhoda, who says that she ‘has no face’ and avoids looking at its reflection, Jinny is eager to examine her entire body in the looking glass. She cannot stand seeing only the reflection of her head in the smaller looking glass, as that contradicts her concept of being a discrete and whole entity:

*I hate the small looking-glass on the stairs,’ said Jinny. ‘It shows our heads only; it cuts off our heads. [...] So I skip up the stairs past them, to the next landing, where the long glass hangs and I see myself entire. I see my body and head in one now [...].’*²¹⁵

Unlike Rhoda, who refuses to acknowledge her material existence in the world, for Jinny the look into the mirror is a confirmation of her feelings of being ‘one’ and ‘complete’. She does not experience a ‘shock of recognition’ when seeing her own reflection or being looked at by another person, as these occurrences only enforce her own self-image. For her, the mirror is a means of self-assertion, just like the admiring glances of other people. However, this already indicates that the mirror as a device of confirmation only works if one entertains a favourable image of oneself. Even Jinny, who is so secure in the knowledge of her own self and identity, needs preparation before she takes a glance at herself in the mirror. She learns that when she catches sight of her reflection in the window of the tube unawares: “*I am at the heart of life. But look – there is my body in the looking-glass. How solitary, how shrunk, aged! [...] Little animal that I am, sucking my flanks in and out with fear, I stand here, palpitating,*

²¹³ Ibid., p. xi

²¹⁴ Woolf, *The Waves*, p. 16.

²¹⁵ Ibid., p. 29 et seq.

trembling".²¹⁶ She is temporarily shocked by what she sees, since the reflection is inconsistent with her self-image for the first time in her life. However, she quickly steadies herself and asserts that she had slipped only for a little moment and that this will not happen again, as she otherwise always braces and prepares herself before she looks at her reflection. This is a typically modernist use of the mirror symbolic, for it hints at the significance of personal perspective. Mirrors do not necessarily show us the truth, but "*they reflect back, Woolf suggests, what one sets out to see*".²¹⁷ The last episode of Jinny examining herself in the mirror even raises the question of whether a thing like an absolute truth or reality even exists. Here, we find her sitting at her desk and closely examining her aged and faded features:

*Now I turn grey; now I turn gaunt; but I look at my face at midday sitting in front of the looking-glass in broad daylight, and note precisely my nose, my chin, my lips that open too wide and show too much gum. But I am not afraid.*²¹⁸

By acknowledging her changed appearance and adapting her self-image in accordance with it, she manages to re-interpret what is reflected back to her. As hedonistic and physical as Jinny may be, the mirror does no longer hold any terror for her; instead, she incorporates the reflection she sees into her sense of self-hood. With that depiction, Woolf asserts that everything depends on the personal approach and perspective. The mirror does not define who we are – it simply reflects our own preconceptions of our identity. The sovereignty of interpretation always lies with the perceiving individual.

The downside of a world that relies entirely on subjective interpretation, however, is that nobody is privy to the perspective of the other. In that way, *The Waves* as a novel "*dramatizes the fact that even our most intimate relationships are flawed by our limited access to other minds*"²¹⁹ which is a recurrent topic in Virginia Woolf's work. In both Jinny and Rhoda's experiences with mirrors, the uncertainty of the 'self' is displayed. This trend of diversification that became apparent at the onset of modernism, applies

²¹⁶ Ibid., p. 148.

²¹⁷ Flint, 2000, p. xxix.

²¹⁸ Virginia Woolf, *The Waves*, p. 170.

²¹⁹ Flint, 2000, p. xxxvi.

even more to society today. Our sense of self is “*assailed from within and without*”²²⁰ at the same time. From the outside, the individual is approached with a multitude of norms, rules, expectations and demands while on the inside it is often riddled with anxiety and doubt. As Woolf suggest in *The Waves*, the self, therefore, is a fluid and transient concept and entity. The example of Rhoda shows that a stable self cannot be found within the other, as the other only reflects our own demeanour back to us like a mirror, and her depiction of Jinny makes it clear that it cannot be located in the body either, as a body is subject to aging processes or other alterations.²²¹ As is the prerogative and tradition of the modernist novel, it raises a variety of questions that remain largely unanswered. *The Waves*, as indeed any of Woolf’s works, is descriptive, not normative. At best, the reader is provided with vantage points for reflection on what the self might be. Everyone will have to peer inside of their own souls (or minds), take the things he or she approves of and mould them into a coherent self. Essentially, one is left with a constructionist perspective – the individual is burdened with the task of self-definition as well as the establishment and maintenance of a stable identity.

²²⁰ Ibid., p. xxvii.

²²¹ Cf. Ibid.

12. Evaluation and concluding remarks

Fiction is like a spider's web, attached ever so slightly perhaps, but still attached to life at all four corners.

- Virginia Woolf, from *A Room of One's Own* –

A student of literature and literary criticism is often confronted with the question of what the utility in studying such a subject is and (deriving from that question) what the utility of reading fiction in general is. Is it not just an idle past-time, escapism, an intellectual escapade that has no practical purpose in our daily lives? At times, literature can seem too aloof and detached from reality to be able to comment on it, let alone to impact it in any significant way. This is the issue the opening quotation by Virginia Woolf alludes to. What she maintains is that, ideally, all fiction pertains to reality in some form. It can mirror it, mimic it, portray it, describe it, and analyse it. However pronounced this attachment may be in an individual literary work, it serves to make a statement about phenomena and entities in real life. Even a Dadaistic novel or a drama by Samuel Beckett in their seeming detachedness from our perceptions of reality can serve as a counter draft to the reality we inhabit. By showing us how the world is not, they make a statement about reality. In that way, fiction is indeed like a spider's web which is attached to life, and thus, sensitive to all its tremors and trepidations. One of the writers who was most susceptible to these disturbances and was therefore also most apt to translate it into fiction was Virginia Woolf herself. This holds especially true for her treatment and portrayal of all issues concerning consciousness, identity, perception, image and self-image. Her innovative approach to the exploration of the mind has provided us with many insights into the workings of the human psyche and consciousness. It can be said that this range of topics is one of the most pervasive in her entire fictional work. Her celebrated masterpieces like *To the Lighthouse*, *Orlando*, *Mrs. Dalloway*, and especially *The Waves* all evolve around such themes. However, these issues have been put to words by Virginia Woolf most emphatically in the condensed form of the short story, five of which have been selected for analysis in the thesis at

hand. To stay within the frame of the metaphor, each of these stories represents an intricately woven spider's web of impressions and perceptions and is attached to life by threads of metaphor and symbolism.

As is laid out in the opening remarks, it has been the objective of this thesis to examine Woolf's understanding of the self, identity and consciousness as it is portrayed in her short fiction, as well as to establish a link between her take on these topics and her frequent usage of mirror symbolism. Preceding the actual literary analysis of the selected texts is a number of chapters of a more general, introductory nature. Firstly, an overview of different concepts of the self and of reality in different literary epochs is provided (Ch. 2, Concepts of the self and reality in fiction) in order to be able to categorize Woolf's own approach. That chapter also describes how the impetus for modernism and its concept of the self derives from socio-economic changes and scientific breakthroughs of that time. By means of comparing Virginia Woolf's take on these phenomena with that of her literary predecessors, contemporaries and successors, it is shown what exactly is different and innovative about her approach, how she compares to the writers of her time and what impact her ideas and concepts had on literary currents, authors that succeeded her and her contemporaries. Moreover, this chapter especially emphasizes the modernist take on reality and the self as opposed to classical realist positions which puts Woolf's own ideas into a literary context. It might have been interesting to include an examination of pre-modern and Renaissance literature with their respective portrayals of selfhood. Since the comparison with her immediate literary predecessors was sufficient to distinguish the novelty of the modernist approach, however, that proved not to be essential for the purpose of this thesis.

Since one analytical dimension of this paper is the use of the mirror symbol in Virginia Woolf's works, a chapter on the literary term 'symbol' in general and on the history of the mirror symbol in particular has been included into it. The purpose of the general overview was to establish exactly what is meant by the term 'symbol' and to examine how symbols distinguish a work of fiction from a mere re-production of life in words and thus give a text depth and meaning. To recognize this is a prerequisite for the subsequent analysis of Woolf's works. Naturally, the brief sketch of the history of the mirror symbol can not by any standards be comprehensive but rather serves to

emphasize the ambiguity and versatility of said symbol. It is important to keep in mind that, since the mirror has been one of the most frequently used literary symbols since antiquity, many possible meanings, connotations and references have clustered around it. The mirror is the chameleon within the world of the literary symbols and its ambiguity can easily lure one into making hasty assumptions and, in turn, arriving at unfounded interpretations. And indeed, every instance in which Woolf employed the mirror symbolic differs from the next; no two usages are quite the same. However, all these instances share a common trait. All of them, whether overtly or indirectly, point to a cluster of topics revolving around the self. This suggests that each use of the mirror stands for another aspect of Woolf's idea of selfhood and the self's interaction with others. This thesis has postulated and attempted to prove that there is a meaningful link between the two. This assertion is not only supported by the results of the literary analysis which will be summarized below but is also re-enforced by the data taken from Woolf's letters and diaries, which are examined in greater detail in Chapter 4 (The autobiographical legacy of Virginia Woolf). In addition to this, Chapter 3 (Psychoanalysis and its influence on modernist literature) provides a thematic excursion into the topic of Woolf's knowledge of and affiliation with psychoanalysis and its purveyors, focusing especially on the question of whether Woolf was influenced by Freud's concept of the unconscious/subconscious as is indicated by the structure, content and wording of many of her texts. For quite some time it was the predominant opinion amongst Woolf scholars that Freud's theories had little or no impact on Woolf's writing. Newer research, however, has repeatedly pointed out that even though Woolf did not actually read Freud's works herself until rather late in her life, she was nevertheless surrounded with people who were either psychoanalysts themselves, knowledgeable on the topic or at least interested in discussing it frequently inside her Bloomsbury circle of friends and acquaintances. This, in turn, suggests that typical psychoanalytical concepts such as the subconscious or the unconscious did indeed have a considerable impact on her idea of identity and the human mind and how she translated that idea into fiction. Consistently, the concept of hidden layers of the human psyche, of a multi-faceted personality and ambiguous relationships with others is recurrent in Woolf's work, most prominently in her short fiction, as is the mirror symbol which she uses to allude to different aspects of the self or its relation to others. In each of the five short stories that have been selected for analysis, as well as in the passages taken from her novel *The Waves* at least one aspect of Woolf's concept of self-

hood comes to the fore. In the short story *The Legacy*, for instance, the discrepancy between self-perception and hetero perception which exists in most interpersonal relationships is emphasized by using different mirroring techniques. This discrepancy points to the fact that our personality and identity as we perceive it is not necessarily consistent with how others perceive it even though both perceptions might seem equally 'true' to the respective parties. Thus, the self is subject to interpretation and not a fixed entity. Naturally, this does not only apply to our self-image, but also to how we perceive the people around us which is the predominant theme in the story *Lappin and Lapinova*. Here, Woolf challenges the popular belief that human beings are capable of knowing another person for who they truly are. Especially in romantic relationships the two partners supposedly know each other's most intimate thoughts and emotions and understand the innermost core of the other's being. In *Lappin and Lapinova*, Woolf raises the question of whether that is an accurate belief. To what extent can one self know the other? And to what extent do we simply project an ideal onto the other? However, Woolf also touches on the topic of an unstable sense of self-hood that prevails in the female protagonist of the story and is re-enforced by the way she sees herself in the mirror. This theme of the elusive self is a recurrent topic in Woolf's work, especially in her female characters, as it had indeed been in her own life. It is readopted in the short story *The New Dress* in which the heroine's anxiety and insecurity not only undermine her own sense of selfhood but also sabotage her relationship with others. The striking contrast between the two main mirroring episodes in this story indicates that the protagonist's self-perception and the resulting self-assessment depend largely on the concomitant circumstances. Moreover, her uncertainty about herself and how others might perceive it prevents her from interacting with other people in a positive way. This concurs with Woolf's own struggle to maintain a stable sense of self and identity, especially in social settings and is also consistent with the modernist paradigm of the fluctuating self. The construction and deconstruction of a person is taken to the extreme in the story with the characteristic title *The Lady in the Looking-Glass*. It shows that reality and fiction are similar in how they are created by the reader/observer. There is no hint in the story as to which picture of the heroine is accurate. Instead, Woolf reveals that our reality and with it our own identity and those of the people around us are largely constructed and deconstructed in our minds. It is the ultimate assertion of her

statement that reality is far from being verifiable, “*far from being like this*”²²². This quote from her essay *Modern Fiction* reverberates with Woolf’s fiercest internal struggle. On the one hand, she did not believe in an objective truth or reality, but on the other hand she never gave up the quest for meaning in a chaotic world. The same applied to her notions of self and identity. Whilst she maintains in her fictional works, as well as in her autobiographical documents and in her non-fiction, that the self is prone to constant change and flux and subject to interpretation by oneself and others, she always felt keenly there must be an unalterable core around which the self revolves. This dualism and polarity is reflected most distinctly in one of her earliest works, the short story *The Mark on the Wall*, as well as in her late masterpiece *The Waves* which indicates that it must have been one of the most important themes in her life and her work. It is reflected most prominently in the contrasting characters of Rhoda who lives in constant terror of losing herself and her identity and Jinny who finds a stable sense of self in corporeal things. Whereas for the one the look into the mirror is tormenting, it serves as a means of self-affirmation for the other. This notion of the quest for a stable identity is ever-present in Virginia Woolf’s entire body of work. What she often asked herself, she has put in the mouth of Bernhard, one of the six voices in *The Waves*: “*Who am I? I have been talking of Bernhard, Neville, Jinny, Susan, Rhoda and Louis. Who am I? Am I all of them? Am I one and distinct?*”²²³

Similarly to *The Mark on the Wall*, this question and the duality that reverberates with it are resolved in what Woolf herself called ‘moments of being’. These are moments in which the individual is able to transcend the chaos and constant flux of life, reality and the self and arrives at a feeling of wholeness and unity. This state of being is often symbolized by the image of water in Woolf’s work, a prime example being the interludes in *The Waves*. However, it also occurs in many of her other novels and short stories. As the mirror reflects back to us all our doubts and anxieties about our selves, the water effaces all these questions and provides a sort of transcendental tranquillity to the mind. According to James Naremore, Woolf’s affinity to the element of water did not only manifest itself in the imagery she used but also contributed to her unusual style of writing. Thus, he states that “*reading her, one sometimes has the impression of being immersed so deeply that the people and things in her books become muffled and*

²²² Woolf, *Modern Fiction*, p. 88.

²²³ Woolf, *The Waves*, p. 222.

indistinct, like blurred and ghostly shadows".²²⁴ This description illuminates how the image of water corresponds with Woolf's style of writing and her idea of the 'world without the self' and, thus, serves as a complementary motif to the symbol of the mirror. In the light of this analysis, it seems sadly ironic that Virginia Woolf chose to escape the pains of a fractured and tormented soul by drowning herself. Even though it is not the purpose of the thesis to examine the relationship between different symbols in Woolf's work, investigating this intricate web of motifs might prove to be an interesting project for further research. As to the hypothesis that has been postulated in this paper, it can be said that the detailed textual analysis yielded favourable results and a firm link between Woolf's concept of the self and her use of mirror symbolism has been established. As has been stated above, the thesis at hand is by no means comprehensive on the subject of symbolism in Virginia Woolf's fiction. Even though it stands to gain much by further research, it presents a first successful excursion into her entrancing world. At the centre of this world and at the heart of her writing is the "*small, luminous creature in the corner of the mirror*"²²⁵. According to Virginia Woolf, of this figure in the mirror all we can ever know are "*scraps, orts and fragments*"²²⁶ held in momentary harmony and sympathy. That is the essence of her writing.

²²⁴ James Naremore, *The World without a Self. Virginia Woolf and the Novel*, New Haven: Yale University Press, 1973, p. 2.

²²⁵ Joanne Trautmann Banks, *Introduction to Congenial Spirits*, in: Woolf, Virginia, *Congenial Spirits. Selected Letters*, edited by Joanne Trautmann Banks and with a new preface by Hermione Lee, London: Pimlico/Random House, 2003, p. xiv.

²²⁶ From Virginia Woolf, *Between the Acts*, Harcourt Brace & Company: Orlando, 1970, p. 192.

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